

High Dosage Vitamin C in Allergy

By

SIMON L. RUSKIN, M.D.

NEW YORK, NEW YORK

IN a recent editorial in the Journal of the American Medical Association discussing the anti-spasmodic action of "hypotensive" extracts on smooth muscle, it was pointed out that while many clinical reports on the usefulness of pancreatic extracts existed in the literature, the actual experimental demonstration showed no effect that could not be attributed to the preservatives used in the extracts. The very cogent conclusion was that "the results of these investigations are but another demonstration that clinical results, even though apparently beneficial, are not in themselves a definite proof of the effectiveness of the drug employed. The pharmacodynamic effect of a substance can, with greater accuracy, be demonstrated in properly controlled animal experiments".

It is precisely this situation that has beset the question of Vitamin C in allergy. Clinical data is itself subject to so many uncontrollable factors that at best, they must be considered only as of secondary importance, unless supported by both animal pharmacologic control and physiological rationale.

While clinical observation is simple and subjective, pharmacologic control is expensive, painstaking and objective. Physicians who readily give an opinion on the value or lack of value of Vitamin C in allergy are not so ready to spend a year on animal experimental confirmation to back up their easily arrived at conclusions.

When in June 1938, I published in the *Annals of Otolaryngology, Rhinology and Laryngology*, a paper on Calcium Cevitamate in the Treatment of Acute Rhinitis, I recorded one hundred clinical cases of vasomotor rhinitis associated with the common cold and various allergic states treated with large doses of calcium vitamin C. The allergic patients seemed particularly to benefit. There was at that time no suggested plan of experimental control and years were spent probing various methods. In the meantime, clinical opinion took the usual course of finding subjective proponents and objectors when in 1939, I ran across the technique of Sollman and Gilbert for the microscopic observation of bronchiolar reactions. Here at last was an almost ideal procedure for evaluating the antihistamine effect of Vitamin C as well as the influence of Vitamin C on various anti allergic therapeutic agents.

The technique was difficult and required nine months of special training of a skillful technician. The improvements in procedure and the detailed description was read before the American Chemical Society in 1940. Two years later, Holmes also reported before the same Society, favorable clinical results obtained in the treatment of allergy by large doses of Vitamin C.

During the interim, a rather large literature developed around the detoxifying action of Vitamin C in regard to arsenicals and Bundesen et al showed that Vitamin C applied on patch tests locally to the skin of arsenic sensitive patients, strikingly diminished the allergic reaction to arsenic, whereas the oral administration of Vitamin C did not influence the patch test. Duke University investigators also arrived at the conclusion that oral doses of Vitamin C did not affect the intradermal or scratch test sensitivity. The inadequacy of this type of experimental approach becomes obvious when viewed in the light of Bundeson's work which showed that arsenic sensitivity was reduced by Vitamin C even though the skin test was not affected, except when the Vitamin C was locally applied. Oser and Sulzberger showed that scorbutic guinea pigs were definitely more sensitive to arsphenamine than animals kept on a normal or high Vitamin C.

Unfortunately, we do not today possess a method of testing the immediate requirements of Vitamin C arising under various physiologic conditions. Neither the fragility test nor the saturation test supplies this data. Bronstein showed that adrenalin accelerates the appearance of scurvy and Cannon established the fact that emotions mobilize adrenalin.

The intimate relationship between emotional excitement and allergic reactions is a most common experience, and the increase of Vitamin C requirements likewise become obvious. As yet, we have no method of experimentally demonstrating this relationship other than the antihistamine reaction.

Attacking the problem from a physiological angle, I published a paper on Histamine Adrenalin Balance, pointing out the role of calcium ascorbate.

There remained a further biochemical approach for support of our clinical observations. This was particularly suitable in the study of hay fever reactions since the outstanding clinical feature was the disturbance of tissue fluid balance. The rhinorrhea represents a considerable amount of fluid loss over the period of the hay fever season and simultaneously was the most obvious symptom by which to record improvement.

In studying the mechanism of fluid balance, it was clear that urea formation was the predominantly physiologic factor. An analysis of the biochemistry of urea formation shows the amino acid arginine to be the main source. Through the breakdown of arginine through citrulline and ornithine, we have the urea cycle. It was therefore, startling to find that the antihistamine effect of arginine was independently observed by Landau and Gay. In starting arginine on the urea cycle arginase is

the essential enzyme. Arginase is activated by ascorbic acid and thus we again come to a connecting link biochemically between ascorbic acid and allergy. The diuretic effect of Vitamin C is thus also explained. This diuretic action was also clinically observed by some of the patients and probably plays an important role in the clinical improvement.

The clinical use of Vitamin C in the various intoxications such as lead shown by Marchmont, arsenic shown by Bundesen et al, arsphenamine demonstrated by Oser and Sulzberger are interesting when viewed from the angle that histamine shock shows pathologically similar pictures to that of the intoxications. Moon has brilliantly described the pathologic physiology of these conditions.

Similarly the action of Vitamin C in promotion of wound healing and in the treatment of non surgical illness are intimately related to its antihistamine effect. The bibliography of the papers describing the action of Vitamin C in these conditions numbers well over three hundred. This has been carried to the point where Holman recommends administration of large doses of Vitamin C to all patients entering a hospital for medical or surgical care.

It is therefore not unexpected to find Holmes in 1942 confirming my earlier finding of 1938 that large doses of Vitamin C were beneficial in the treatment of seasonal allergy. In my series of one hundred cases of acute rhinitis and vasomotor rhinitis treated by calcium cevitamate, the patients received injections of 3 cc of a 15% solution of calcium ascorbate. The Vitamin C dosage in each injection was 450 mg. In view of the fact that the vitamin was given parenterally, it should be considered as equal to 1000 mg. by mouth. This dosage produced striking results as shown in my report. However, the pharmacological dose in those days was considered to be 40-60 mgs. So, when I originally presented calcium ascorbate as a therapeutic source of calcium for the program of the American Chemical Society, it was rejected on the basis that a therapeutic dose of calcium ascorbate containing 450 mg. of ascorbic acid was so far above the accepted 40-60 mg. that they could see no basis for admitting it as a therapeutic calcium salt. Today, of course, we know that in tuberculosis and acute infectious diseases, a daily requirement of 1000 mg. is frequent. The United States Pharmacopeia also makes the statement that no toxic dose for man or animal has yet been established.

The dosage of 40-60 mg. of Vitamin C is really a prophylactic antiscorbutic dose rather than a therapeutic dose. Most interesting is the finding of Yoshekama who showed that the administration of daily doses of 2.5 mg. of Vitamin C while guinea pigs are being allergized will increase the allergy; moderate doses have no effect and large doses, 100 mg. will have an inhibiting influence. This observation is in direct line with my own experience and that of Holmes. Clinical observations therefore on patients receiving small doses of Vitamin C for treatment of allergy, is not to be considered relevant to the question.

The striking difference between the effect of a single large dose and of moderate repeated doses of ascorbic

acid in Vitamin C deficiency was demonstrated by Mouriquand and Edel. They found that a single dose of 50 mg. ascorbic acid doubled the survival time of guinea pigs with developed scurvy. Even 25 mg. had a life prolonging effect. Weekly doses of 10 mg. caused temporary improvement for five weeks followed by a sudden relapse and death. This experimental work throws further light on the discrepancies in clinical reports where small prophylactic doses are compared with the large doses recommended by Holmes and myself.

During the hay fever season in 1944, a special clinical study was made on vitamin C tablets containing in three tablets, a dose of 250 mg. vitamin C and 1 mg. thiamin. Kim and Lee demonstrated that vitamin B during an allergization has an inhibiting effect on anaphylactic shock in guinea pigs.

The patients represented two groups; Group A, those receiving only the special vitamin, and a second group B given the special vitamin tablets and desensitization. As a control, the same patients' condition in 1943 was used. Pollen counts for 1944 and 1943 were recorded during the periods that the patients returned for observation. In general, it was found that patients who felt well, did not take the time to report at the office, so that the follow-up notes were really showing the less favorable days. A general questionnaire was therefore composed to summarize comparative data and the totals tabulated, as follows:

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever?
2. Do you have food allergies as well?
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season?
4. When did you start taking the special vitamin C tablets?
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms?
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better
 results?
9. Do you think the special vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach?
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms?
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better
 than previous years?

13. Did you also receive hay fever injections?
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years?
15. Would you consider the vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks?

Remarks:

Name:

Occupation:

Of the 27 cases studied, 11 patients received simultaneously pollen desensitization. In this group 9 reported that the combination of desensitization plus the vitamin C B tablets was more effective than desensitization alone as received in previous years, thus indicating that they had experienced a beneficial result from the added vitamin C therapy.

Among those receiving only vitamin C B tablets there were 2 who had received desensitization in previous years and had this year received only vitamin C B pills. In this group both reported benefits which were greater than that derived from desensitization in previous years. Twenty showed benefits with vitamin C B pills greater than other previous remedies or any treatment. As a result of this tabulation, we can conclude that group A showed 11 with improvement over previous years. Group B showed 9 with improvement over previous years. In view of the fact that the total pollen count in 1944 was 115% of average, whereas that for 1943 was 88% of average, we can readily see that although 1944 was 27% higher in pollen concentration than in 1943, 74% of patients receiving vitamin C B tablets felt better in 1944 than they did in 1943.

Similarly in answer to question 12, twenty of the twenty-seven reported feeling better than in previous years giving 74% of improvement for this group.

Question No. 14 which compares the benefit of hay fever injections in previous years, 9 patients had been helped, whereas 14 had not been helped and 3 were having their hay fever for the first season. One patient reported "not much improvement". Question No. 14 is a very revealing one insofar as it indicates a relatively low percentage of satisfactory results from desensitization alone.

Question 15 is still more striking since 24 of the 27 patients felt that the vitamin C B tablets modified their hay fever attacks.

On Question 9, here again 23 of the 27 patients reported vitamin C B tablets were helpful.

On Question 8, a large dosage was started from the very onset in 8 patients. Of the remaining 19 cases, increasing the dosage gave a better result in 12 patients, thus showing that the high vitamin C dosage of 9 tablets a day makes a very definite difference in interpreting clinical benefits. This is in direct conformity with the experimental work cited earlier in this paper as well as the experience of Dr. Holmes and myself in my previous publication of the Use of Calcium Cevitamate in The Treatment of Acute Rhinitis and Allergic Conditions. Virtually all of the 100 cases reported, experienced definite benefit. In that series, vitamin C was given parenterally, each dose representing approximately 450 mg. of vitamin C. The rationale

of the use of large doses of ascorbic acid in upper respiratory disturbances including vasomotor rhinitis and asthma was presented for the first time. This was the first introduction of large dose vitamin C therapy.

Question 10. . . . Six patients indicate that there was some irritation of the stomach ranging from slight indigestion and uncertainty, and one case of hives and irritation of the lids. Twenty-one of the patients complained of no discomfort whatever. None of the patients with the exception of the one suffering from hives felt irritation sufficient to warrant discontinuance of treatment.

In response to Question No. 11, nine of the patients reported an increase in urination during the time of the administration of Vitamin C. This is in itself a difficult question to answer since most patients would not notice an increased urination unless it was something quite definite. Of all these patients reporting an increase in urination, we observe they also reported in question 12 that they felt better than in previous years thus indicating that a diuretic effect was observed in those cases that reported improvement from C B tablets.

In Question No. 7 which indicates the number of tablets used, it was interesting to note that all those patients who were receiving 9 tablets daily, only 2 patients reported any stomach irritation; 1 indicated slight heart-burn; the other slight stomach irritation. Of the remainder reporting stomach irritation were all those who received only 3 tablets daily, thus indicating that it was not the size of the dose which caused the complaint, but rather a special sensitivity to Vitamin C itself. This, of course, can be dependent on whether or not the patient was suffering from some other form of gastric disturbance such as hyper acidity.

In reply to question No. 6 comparing the attacks of 1944 to previous years, we find that 17 patients considered their attacks less than in previous years; 5 considered their attacks the same as in previous years; 1 complained of a worse season than in previous years; 2 were in their first season and so had no basis for comparison; 1 patient stopped treatment early because of sensitivity to Vitamin C, and 1 patient felt the attacks to be somewhat less but severe.

Question 5. The first day of the attack of this season's hay fever was requested in the questionnaire, but was confused with the duration of the hay fever suffering by some of the patients.

Question 3 inquired as to the frequency of asthmatic attacks; 12 of the 27 patients suffered also from asthma. Of these, 8 patients replied in answer to question 12 that they felt better than in previous years; 2 reported worse than last year; 2 reported the same as in previous years. In view of the fact that asthma is a severe disease, it is highly interesting to learn that 8 of the 12 patients showed improvement. This can be considered as a relatively high percentage of therapeutic success for this intractable disease and clinically substantiates the experimental work showing the anti-histamine effect of Vitamin C. Of 8 of the asthmatics benefited, 5 were taking 6 or 9 tablets daily, thus showing that the dosage employed was a vital factor in the therapeutic success.

In further evaluating the benefits of Vitamin C in allergy, it is interesting to note that 14 of the 27 patients suffered from food allergies as well. Of these fourteen, 11 reported in answer to question 12 that they were better than in previous years; 2 were not sure because of the first season; and 1 reported that he was worse this season. This high incidence of general improvement associated with both food and pollen sensitivity is a further indication of the usefulness of Vitamin C, since part of the discomfort of an allergic patient generally is attributed to food allergies current at the same time, particularly in the case of asthmatics.

This survey has thus brought out a most valuable accumulation of data not hitherto surveyed from the critical angle here presented. I have felt that a completely untreated group was unnecessary for control since the average pollen count between the year 1943 and 1944 showed over 25% increased pollen content allowing the conclusion that a completely untreated group would probably show an increased severity of attacks during 1944 as against 1943. It is apparent that patients who are not receiving any treatment at all are unwilling to spend their time coming to the physician simply for observation. The following is a report of the pollen count as taken at the Jewish Hospital of Brooklyn:

Pollen Counts
Ragweed Season of 1943

	August	September	October
1	0	235	2*
2	1	233	4
3	2	106*	3
4	rain	45	4
5	0	61	1
6	0	60	1
7	6	163*	7
8	3*	76	4
9	rain	144	6
10	4*	32	0
11	27	56	1
12	2	34	1
13	rain	20	0
14	39	28*	0
15	25	51	rain
16	28	137*	rain
17	37	12*	0
18	33	22	rain
19	32	18	0
20	66	48	
21	17	5*	
22	32	10*	
23	158	27*	
24	110	7	
25	119	4	
26	142	6	
27	rain	36	
28	98	26	
29	22	19	
30	118	rain	
31	236		
	1357	1721	45

* incomplete count due to showers.
Average total ragweed 1936 to 1943 3,531
Total ragweed for 1943 (July 14 to Oct. 20) 3,115
Total ragweed for 1943 (Aug. 9 to Sept. 28) 3,047
Pollen concentration for Ragweed Season 1943, 88% of average

Pollen Counts
Ragweed Season of 1944

	August	September	October
1	0	106	3
2	rain	346	3
3	rain	354	3
4	3	238	2
5	0	319	1
6	rain	312	1
7	4	455	1
8	3	279	2
9	9	68	0
10	19	50	1
11	26	43	0
12	25	rain	
13	24	rain	
14	29	rain	
15	32	75	
16	4*	19	
17	7*	25	
18	82	16	
19	42	2*	
20	40	10	
21	38*	33	
22	93	16	
23	75	13	
24	75	12	
25	52	9	
26	43	14	
27	51	4	
28	56*	2*	
29	152	11	
30	161	7	
31	131		
	1276	2838	17

* incomplete count due to showers.
Average total ragweed 1936 to 1944 3,599
Total ragweed for 1944 (July 21 to Oct. 10) 4,139
Total ragweed for 1944 (Aug. 9 to Sept. 28) 4,086
Pollen concentration for Ragweed Season 1944, 115% of average

In answer to the remarks, 9 patients made statements relevant to improvement as follows:

Remarked by:

R.F. —“Hay fever attacks vary so widely from day to day that to correlate the effect of the vitamin C with the physical condition is difficult. It was not a complete cure.”

E.H. —“I was much more comfortable during this past hay fever period and also had better after effects.”

W.L. —“Better general condition.”

G.E.P.—“Improvement better than over previous years, but I did not have medical treatment before for same.”

S.R. —“Did not take the pills from Sept. 21 to Sept. 28th, and missed them and sneezed during that period.”

F.B.S.—“This year the hay fever attacks started later for me than any previous year, namely Sept. 3rd. Also, instead of losing weight during the season, I gained about four pounds.”

F.W. —“I have only had about four or five very bad attacks this season due to the vitamin C tablets. I must emphasize the fact that I felt better this season for the first time in twenty-five years.”

G.B. —“I definitely believe that the tablets were helpful.”

B.B. —“Went without pills one day and had running nose again. Took only two tablets in the evening.”

Four indicated reason for lack of improvement as follows:

Remarked by:

M.M. —“I was at the White Mountains for three weeks and had a few light attacks in the morning, but have had two bad attacks since returning.”

A.R. —“Due to a bad season I was not as well as the past two years.”

A.S. —“I was more exposed to pollen this year because of military training.”

S.C. —“Treatment discontinued because of hives.”

The remainder made no relevant remarks, but indicated their replies in the preceding questions:

Remarked by:

G.P.C.—“I have had a bad sinus infection. Dr. Ruskin operated on me in February and I have had a series of injections after, until June.”

N.H. —“Had dust injections.”

M.J.H.—“I started taking the tablets late in the season.”

R.R. —“Vitamin C tablets stopped after two weeks. Now taking nucleic acid powder with relief.”

B.W. —“Also received dust injections.”

R.B. —“For more than a year I have been taking daily doses of combined vitamins.”

P.S. —“I took only a few of the tablets.”

A much more comprehensive story of the therapeutic effect is evident from the progress notes and history of the cases which follow.

Case I

R. B.

419 E. 57 St.

New York, N. Y.

History

Has had hay fever and asthma for twenty years.

Has had very little benefit from any therapy including desensitizatoin.

Examination

Nasal Mucosa—Hyperplastic

Turbinates —Inferior turbinates hypertrophied

Discharge —Mucoïd discharge in both middle and superior meati on both sides

Bilateral hyperplastic pan-sinusitis

Therapy

5/19/44—Allergy testing with 4+ to dust, feathers, ragweed and Timothy.

Started series of catarrhal vaccine and protein injections.

7/4/44 —Started C.B. Pills, I T.I.D.

7/15/44—No irritation of stomach; an increase of urine.

8/4/44 —Less sneezing, prob- 1944 pollen count 0
ably once a day. 1943 pollen count 0

8/15/44—Patient states general condition seems bet- 1944 pollen count 32
ter. 1943 pollen count 25

8/30/44—Patient states he has had fewer attacks, but more severe, causing 1944 pollen count 161 physical exhaustion. 1943 pollen count 118

Clinical Summary

5/19/44—Nasal mucosa moderately hyperplastic; moderate nasal obstruction. No acute signs.

7/4/44 —Mucosa engorged, moderate amount of sero-mucinous discharge.

7/15/44—Nasal mucosa moderately engorged, discharge diminished. Nasal ventilation fair.

8/15/44—Nasal mucosa moderately congested; very little nasal discharge; nasal ventilation good.

8/30/44—Nasal ventilation has remained fair; slight sero-mucoid discharge.

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 19 years knowingly, however, no symptoms appeared while on the west coast, (1930-1933).

2. Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.

3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Occasionally.

4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? July.

5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? Summer of 1925.

6. Would you consider your attacks

a. worse

c. less more severe.

than previous years?

7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 per day.

8. Did increasing the dosage give

b. same

less frequent, but much

a. same

b. better no increase

results?

9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C Tablets were

a. no help X

b. helpful

10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.

11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Questionable.

12. Did you feel generally

a. same

b. worse X but attacks were less frequent than previous years.

c. better

than previous years?

13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? Yes.

14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Questionable.

15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? No.

Remarks: for more than a year I have been taking daily doses of combined vitamins.

Name: R. B.

Occupation: Life Insurance Program Planning.

Case II

B. B.

171 Grafton St.

Brooklyn, N. Y.

Age 19

History

Sneezing about 1 year. At about age 10 or 11, had frequent colds. All year round, complains of post nasal drip. Sneezing started in July last year. Worse in rainy weather. No chest symptoms. No allergies in family. No history of food allergies.

Examination

Mucosa —Hyperplastic.
Tonsils —Removed.
Turbinates—Inferior turbinates hypertrophied.
Discharge —Mucoid discharge both middle meati, more pronounced on right.

Therapy

6/13/44—Sneezing for past 2 weeks.
Allergy testing 4+ to ragweed, timothy.
7/4/44 —Started C.B. Pills, 1 T.I.D.
8/24/44—Increased to 2 T.I.D. 1944 pollen count 75
Occasional h e a r t
burn. Nose not run-
ning. Generally better. 1943 pollen count 110
9/11/44—P.H. 7—C.B. Pills, 3 T.I.D.
Generally better.
Went without tablets
one day and had run-
ning nose. Immedi-
ately after taking 2
tablets, nose stopped 1944 pollen count 43
running. 1943 pollen count 56

Clinical Summary

6/13/44—Nasal mucosa acutely engorged; nasal ventilation markedly diminished; thin serous discharge.
7/1/44 —Findings similar to previous examination.
8/24/44—Nasal mucosa hyperplastic, but not engorged; slight mucoid discharge; nasal ventilation fair.
9/11/44—Nasal mucosa hyperplastic, but not congested; very little discharge; good nasal ventilation.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN
ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever?
First season.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
4. When did you start taking the Special C tablets?
July.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms?
From end of May through summer.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less
 than previous years? (First season.)
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
3 a day subsequently 6, then increased to 9 a day.

8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better X
 results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful X
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? Slight heart burn.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better
 than previous years? First season.
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years?
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.
Remarks: Went without pills one day and had running nose again. Took only two tablets in the evening.
Name: Miss B. B.
Occupation: Student.
S. C.
6822 Fleet Street
Forest Hills, N. Y.

Age 51

History

cc: Has ragweed sensitivity for last 20 years. Otherwise has no complaints.
Hives occasionally.

Examination

Nasal Mucosa —Hyperplastic.
Septum —Deflected to right.
Inferior Turbinate—Hypertrophied.
Tonsils —Removed.
Drums —Retracted and thick.

Therapy

8/3/44 —Allergy testing.
High allergic to foods; also dust, feathers, Ragweed and Timothy. 1944 pollen count—
rain
Given adrenalin to control hives due to the testing. 1943 pollen count 2
Started C.B. Pills, 1 T.I.D.
8/17/44—Complains of hives around the eyes, due, patient states, to the C.B. pills. Also complaining of slight irritation of the stomach. 1944 pollen count 7*
1943 pollen count 37
8/31/44—Patient called by phone to state that she is having very little sneezing and is feeling improved, more so than at any other year. No in-

crease in dosage 1944 pollen count 131
given. 1943 pollen count 236
*incomplete count due to showers.

Clinical Summary

8/3/44 —Nasal mucosa engorged; fairly profuse rhinorrhoea.
8/17/44—There is angio-neurotic edema of both upper and lower lids; nasal mucosa not engorged and there is no rhinorrhoea.
9/3/44 —Patient reported by telephone recurrence of hives, discontinued treatment herself.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever?
12 years.
1. Do you have food allergies as well?
3. Do you have athmatic attacks during the hay fever season?
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? This year, by your advice.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms?
Aug. 20, 1944.
6. Would you consider your attacks Treatment
a. worse discontinued.
b. same
c. less
than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
3 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give It gave me hives
a. same around the eyes.
b. better
results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tables were
a. no help Very little help in sneezing.
b. helpful
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach?
I presume so.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking
tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Yes
12. Did you feel generally
a. same Almost the same
b. worse
c. better
than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous
years? No.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modi-
fied your hay fever attacks? Very little.

Remarks: Treatment discontinued because of hives.
Name: Mrs. S. C.

Occupation: Housewife.

G. P. C.
201 Crown Street
Brooklyn, New York

Age 35

History

Post nasal drip with right nasal discharge, chiefly greenish with odor. Duration 3 years. Onset with past

bladder trouble. Had ulcer in rectum. Had polyps removed. Had asthmatic attack in Florida. Was allergic to feathers and eggs in childhood. Found allergic to dust and ozite. X-rays show infection of right antrum. Has headache on right side. Has chills and fever with mucous in stools with foul odor. Occasional vertigo. No ear complaints. No sore throat. Pain in knees and elbows with sensation of stiffness in muscles and tiredness in back of head. Feels achy in feet. Generally tired. Typhoid, measles and mumps in childhood.

Examination

Mucosa —Hyperplastic.
Discharge —Muco-purulent discharge in right middle meatus. Both middle meati open, left middle meatus shows mucoid discharge.
Septum —Shows moderate spur posteriorly on right side.
Turbinates —Hypertrophy of posterior tip or inferior turbinates.
Buccal Mucosa—Normal.
Gingiva shows low grade irritation.
Teeth —Calcium deficiency.
Tongue —Papillae slightly hypertrophied; posterior portion appears coated. Mucosa surface slightly hypertrophic.
Tonsils —Removed. Extensive scarring of both anterior pillars; uvula has been removed.
Glands —Enlarged, more pronounced on left side.
Epiglottis —Lymphoid tissue at base of tongue.
Aryt. —Muco-purulent discharge adherent to vocal chords.
Larynx —Otherwise negative.

Therapy

11/8/43—Examination with allergy testing
Milk 1+ Cocoa 1+
Eggs 1+ Feathers 4+
Dust 4+ Ragweed 1+
11/15/43—Right antrum washed with 4+ returns.
12/20/43—Right antrum washed with 4+ returns.
12/27/43—Headache lessened.
2/4/44 —Right antotomy at office.
2/14/44 —Normal recovery.
4/16/44 —Asthmatic condition has improved even with change of weather.
5/1/44 —Asthmatic condition continuing.
5/4/44 —Right antrum washed with zephrian 4+ old pus.
5/15/44 —Started on C.B. pills, 1 T.I.D.
6/1/44 —Attacks lessened.
6/15/44 —Asthmatic attacks stopped entirely.
7/2/44 —No asthmatic attacks since taking C.B. pills.
8/1/44 —No attacks during 1944 pollen count 0 the summer months. 1943 pollen count 0

Clinical Summary

5/15/44—Nasal mucosa congested; thin serous discharge, indicative of dust reaction.

- 6/1/44 —Nasal condition improved; post nasal discharge diminished.
- 6/15/44—Nasal fossae shows good ventilation space; very little congestion; only slight mucoid post nasal discharge.
- 7/2/44 —Nasal breathing excellent; mucous membrane not engorged, slight post nasal discharge.
- 8/1/44 —Nasal space good; mucosa appears fairly normal; slight mucoid discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

- For how many seasons have you had hay fever?
No hay fever.
- Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.
- Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Yes.
- When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? Off and on with other injections.
- When did you first have any hay fever symptoms?
Not sure.
- Would you consider your attacks
 - worse
 - same Asthma attacks stopped.
 - less X
 than previous years?
- How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
1 a day.
- Did increasing the dosage give
 - same
 - better Can't judge.
 results?
- Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - no help
 - helpful X
- Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? None.
- Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? None.
- Did you feel generally
 - same
 - worse
 - better X
 than previous years.
- Did you also receive hay fever injections? I received calcium and histidine.
- Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? No.
- Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Remarks: I have had a bad sinus infection. Dr. Ruskin operated on me in February, and I have had a series of injections after, until June.

Case V

Name: G. P. C.

Occupation: Housewife.

J. C.
39 W. 55 St.
New York, N. Y.

Age 22

History

Post nasal drip for last 8-10 years. Nasal obstruction, chiefly at night, alternating, worse in rainy weather. Has swelling of tissues of forehead. Headaches with nasal obstruction. Heaviness in head. Had steady headache for 19 days recently. Has hay fever in August and also has asthmatic condition. An uncle died of asthma. No hives. No eczema. Stuffiness in ears at times.

Operations: D & C 1½ years ago, Broncho-pneumonia 4-5 years ago.

Examination

Mucosa —Engorged, nasal fossae very much obstructed.

Discharge —Sero-mucoid discharge in both middle meati.

Septum —In mid position.

Transillumination—Moderately diminished on both sides.

Tonsils —Removed.

Therapy

7/27/44—Examination—allergic testing:

Dust	4+	Chocolate	4+
Milk	4+	Feathers	4+
Eggwhite	4+	Timothy	4+
		Ragweed	4+

8/3/44 —Started C. B. Pills, 1944 pollen count—
1 T.I.D. rain

Started hay fever injections. 1943 pollen count 2

8/15/44—Starting first symptoms of hay fever. C.B. Pills, 2 T.I.D.; slight increase in urination. 1944 pollen count 32
1943 pollen count 25

9/5/44 —Sneezing less than in previous years. C.B. Pills, 3 T.I.D. 1944 pollen count 319
No tearing. 1943 pollen count 61

9/15/44—No sneezing. 1944 pollen count 75
1943 pollen count 51

9/20/44—No symptoms for the remainder of the sea- 1944 pollen count 10
season. 1943 pollen count 48

Clinical Summary

8/15/44—Nasal mucosa engorged; nasal fossae markedly obstructed; mucoid discharge.

9/5/44 —Nasal mucosa moderately congested; nasal fossae shows fair breathing space; moderate mucoid discharge.

9/15/44—Nasal fossae fairly clear; mucosa not congested; mucoid discharge slight; patient appears quite comfortable.

9/20/44—Good nasal space; mucosa not engorged; very little nasal discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

- For how many seasons have you had hay fever?
8 years.

Name: S. D.

Occupation: Motion Picture Distributor.

R. F.

385 Central Park W.

New York, New York. Age 31.

History

Hay fever for past ten years, worse for past two years. No food allergies.

Examination

Mucosa —Moderately hyperplastic.
Septum —Deflected to right.
Turbinates —Inferior turbinates hypertrophied.
Tonsils —Removed.
Transillumination—Diminished illumination both sides.

Therapy

6-4-44 —Started C.B Pills 3 T.I.D.

Patient did not return to the office for any treatment but reported by phone and letter that the C.B. Pills seemed to lessen the severity of his attacks. No increase in urine or irritation of the stomach. The same dosage taken throughout the season.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? Badly, for the last two.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? No.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? June, 1944.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? May.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same X
 - c. less
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better
 results? Did not increase.
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C Tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful Slightly.
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better Slightly.
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? Yes.

14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Slightly.

15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Slightly.

Remarks: Hay fever attacks vary so widely from day to day that to correlate the effect of the vitamin "C" with the physical condition is difficult. It was not a complete cure.

Name: R. F.

Occupation: Engineer.

B. G.

73 Avenue

Flushing, L. I.

Age 28

History

Hay fever for two seasons. No food allergies but slight asthmatic attacks during the season.

Examination

Mucosa —Hyperplastic and thickened.
Septum —Moderately deflected.
Turbinates—Inferior turbinates hypertrophied.
Tonsils —Diseased.

Therapy

9-24-44—Started C.B. pills 3 T.I.D.

Patient did not return to office but reported by letter that he feels better this year even though he started the C.B. pills in the middle of the season. States of no irritation to the stomach or of bladder disturbances. Did not take hay fever injections with the C.B. pills.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 2.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? No.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Slight.
4. When did you start taking Special Vitamin C tablets? September.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? 2 years ago.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same X
 - c. less
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 9 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better
 results?

9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C Tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful X
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same X
 - b. worse
 - c. better
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? No.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Remarks: I definitely believe that the tablets were helpful.

Name: B. G.

Occupation: Salesman.

M. H. (Patient is Dr. Ruskin's Bank Teller)

History

Hay fever for the past 35 years.

No food allergies.

No asthmatic attacks.

Examination

No physical examination.

Therapy

9-1-44 —C.B. pills 3 T.I.D. 1944 pollen count 106
 Patient did not return 1943 pollen count 235
 to office but reported
 by phone.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 35 years.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? No.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? Sept. 1, 1944.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? 35 years ago.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less X
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 9 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better X
 results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C Tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful

10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms?
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better X
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? Not this year.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Yes.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attack? Yes.

Remarks: I started taking the tablets late in the season.

Name: M. H.

Occupation: Bank Teller.

N. H.

1307 Sixth Ave.

New York, N. Y. Age 29

History

Has had some trouble for 4 years. Hay fever last summer complicated with asthma and pleurisy. Had a cold with laryngitis a few weeks ago. Had allergy tests 3 years ago. Sensitive to dust.

Appendectomy in March 1944.

Allergic—Acne. Receiving X-ray therapy.

Examination

Pupils react to light and accommodation.

Mucosa —Hyperplastic

Discharge —Mucoid nasal discharge in right middle meatus

Septum —Deflected to right with partial obstruction. Inferior turbinates moderately hypertrophied.

Transillumination—Both antra and right frontal diminished illumination.

Buccal Mucosa —Slightly thickened.

Teeth —Calcium deficiency.

Tonsils —Removed. Small rest on left side.

Pharynx —Shows lymphoid hyperplasia

Glands —Ant. cerv. glands markedly hypertrophied and enlarged, posterior glands enlarged and palpable.

Larynx —Negative.

Right Ear Drum —Thickened and retracted. Posterior ½ opaque.

Left Ear Drum —Thickened and retracted.

Therapy

8-1-44 —Examination and Allergy testing
 Dust 3+ Milk —
 Feathers 2+ Egg —
 Chocolate 1+ Timothy 3+
 Ragweed 4+

1944 pollen count 0

1943 pollen count 0

- 8-3-44 —Started dust and resp. 1944 pollen count—
injections, started C. rain
B. pills 3 T.I.D. 1943 pollen count 2
- 8-7-44 —Relieved of some asth- 1944 pollen count 7
matic attacks with C. 1943 pollen count 6
B. pills.
- 8-11-44—Relieved by taking 3 1944 pollen count 26
tablets when asthmatic 1943 pollen count 27
attack is more severe.
No irritation of sto-
mach or bladder.

Clinical Summary

- 8-3-44 —Nasal mucosa acutely congested; nasal fossae obstructed; moderately profuse sero-mucinous discharge.
- 8-7-44 —Nasal mucosa less congested; moderate nasal breathing space; nasal discharge slight.
- 8-11-44—Nasal fossae clear; very little mucosal congestion; good breathing space; slight nasal discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN
ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever?
Two.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? First year.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? Beginning 2nd year attacks.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms?
2 years ago.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
6 daily increasing to 9 daily—total of 270.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better
 results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C Tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach?
No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. better
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Never had any.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Remarks: Had dust injections.

Name: N. H.

Occupation: Dancer.

Case X

E. C. H.

7200 Ridge Blvd.

Brooklyn, N. Y. Age 65

History

1-19-43—Had a cold in December, but has been sneezing for some time before that. Then noticed left nostril obstruction; now both are obstructed. Eyes feel tired and heavy, slight headache in mornings.

Examination

Mucosa —Hyperplastic.
Mucoid discharge both sides, mucosa engorged obstructing both nasal fossae.

Buccal mucosa—Normal.

Teeth —Well calcified.

Tongue —Smooth.

Tonsils —Small, deeply buried and congested.

Larynx —Congested.

Ears —Both, thickened and retracted.

Therapy

8-28-44—C.B. Pills, 3 T.I.D. 1944 pollen count 56*
1943 pollen count 98

9-10-44—Relieved of sneezing by C.B. Pills. No increase of urination. Patient states she believes they help elimination. 1944 pollen count 50
1943 pollen count 32

9-20-44—No sneezing during 1944 pollen count 10
entire season. 1943 pollen count 48
*incomplete count due to showers.

Clinical Summary

8-28-44—Nasal fossae completely closed; mucosa is engorged; thin serous discharge; profuse, slight eczema of both nasal alae.

9-10-44—Nasal mucosa moderately congested; patient has fair breathing space; slight mucoid discharge.

9-20-44—Nasal fossae clear; mucoid discharge diminished; very little nasal congestion.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN
ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever?
This is the first.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Some.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? Aug. 28th.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms?
This year.

- 6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less
 than previous years?
- 7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
3 tablets 3 times a day continuously.
- 8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same I have a feeling they helped
 - b. better elimination a better formed stool results?
- 9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C Tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful
- 10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach?
Not that I am aware of.
- 11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
- 12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better
 than previous years?
- 13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
- 14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years?
- 15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.
Name: E. C. H.
Occupation: Clerical Work.

Case XI

E. H.
142-02 Franklin Ave.
Flushing, New York. Age 45

History

cc: Has had hay fever for last 16 years, sneezing, rhinitis, nasal obstruction. Onset around August 28th, lasts one month.

Examination

Mucosa —Very much thickened and hyperplastic.

Turbinates —Both inferior and middle turbinates hypertrophied.

Septum —Moderately deflected high to the right and low to the left.

Tonsils —Removed.

Transillumination—Diminished both maxillary and frontals.

Therapy

5-19-44—Started C.V. Pills 1 T.I.D.

7-2-44 —No irritation of stomach. Increase in urination at night.

8-24-44—No increase in dosage.
Patient feeling better, 1944 pollen count 75
very little sneezing. 1943 pollen count 110

9-30-44—Patient states he was more comfortable during the hay fever season than at any other

period. Very little 1944 pollen count 7
sneezing during the 1943 pollen count—rain four weeks.

Clinical Summary

7-2-44 —Nasal mucosa engorged, moderately, moderate muco serous discharge; nasal ventilation poor.

8-24-44—Nasal mucosa hyperplastic, but not engorged; slight mucoid discharge; nasal ventilation fair.

9-30-44—Nasal mucosa not congested; nasal ventilation good; very little mucoid discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

- 1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever?
12 seasons.
- 2. Do you have food allergies as well? Oat, cabbage.
- 3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
- 4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? May 1944.
- 5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms?
Sept. 2.
- 6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less
 than previous years?
- 7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
3 a day.
- 8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better
 than previous years?
- 7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
3 a day.
- 8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better
 results?
- 9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful
- 10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach?
No.
- 11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? During the night only.
- 12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better
 than previous years?
- 13. Did you also receive hay fever injections?
- 14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? No.
- 15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Definitely.
Remarks: I was much more comfortable during the

past hay fever period and also had better after effects.

Name: E. H.

Occupation: Salesman.

E. L.

187 Pinehurst Ave.

New York, N. Y. Age 11½

History

Hay fever for 4 years. Some food allergies.

No asthmatic attacks.

Examination

Mucosa —Congested.

Turbinates—Inferior turbinates occlude both nasal fossae.

Discharge —Profuse serous discharge.

Septum —Nasal septum in midline.

Tonsils —Removed.

Therapy

7-6-44 —Started C.B. pills 1 T.I.D.

First hay fever symptoms in June.

Patient did not return to office, but mother reported by phone that the patient has been greatly benefitted by the C.B. pills. No increase in dosage. No irritation of bladder or stomach.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever. 4.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? July.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? June.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less X
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same X
 - b. better
 results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful X
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better X
 than previous years?

13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.

14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Yes.

15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Name: E. L.

Occupation: Schoolboy. 11½ years old

W. L.

15 E. 36 St.

New York, N. Y. Age 46

History

cc: Hay fever for 30 years with asthmatic attacks.

Examination

Nasal mucosa hyperplastic, septum markedly deflected to right. Bilateral maxillary and ethmoidal sinusitis. Hypertrophic inferior turbinates.

Profuse sero-mucous discharge.

Therapy

6/1/44 —Started C.B. Pills, 1 T.I.D.

6/9/44 —No sneezing since taking pills, no itching. Started hay fever injections.

7/5/44 —Slight increase in urination. Increased to 2 T.I.D.

8/1/44 —No sneezing. General condition improved. 1944 pollen count 0
Increased to 3 T.I.D. 1943 pollen count 0

8/30/44—No sneezing. No asthmatic attacks. 1944 pollen count 161
H.P. 615. 1943 pollen count 118

9/15/44—General condition much better than in 1944 pollen count 75
previous years. 1943 pollen count 51

Clinical Summary

6/9/44 —Nasal mucosa slightly congested; moderate nasal discharge; nasal fossae moderately obstructed.

7/5/44 —Nasal fossae moderately obstructed; slight mucoid discharge; mucosa slightly congested.

8/1/44 —Nasal mucosa not engorged, nasal fossae fairly clear; slight mucoid discharge.

8/30/44—Nasal mucosa not congested; nasal fossae clear; slight mucoid discharge.

9/15/44—Nasal mucosa not congested; nasal fossae quite clear; slight mucoid discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 30 years.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? No.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Yes.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tables? June 1, 1944.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? August 20, 1944.

6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less considering the bad weather.
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
3 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better
 results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Yes.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? Yes.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Yes.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Decidedly.

Remarks: Better general condition.

Name: W. C.

Occupation: Radio Director.

M. M.

215 S. 5th Avenue
New Brunswick, N. J.

History

1935—Frontal pains around eyes radiating to occipitals. At times pains in both cheeks. After nasal operation 6 years ago, developed hay fever, occasional nasal drip, vertigo and neuritis. Occasional pain in ears.

Teeth —Normal.

Tonsils—Diseased.

Bilateral pain sinusitis—polypoid, left antrum 2+

Septum—Shows large post-operative perforation, nasal fossae obstructed.

Therapy

9/1/44 —Started C.B. pills, 1 T.I.D. Started hay fever symptoms August 14th. 1944 pollen count 106
1943 pollen count 235

9/20/44—Some irritation of stomach. Some increase in urination. 1944 pollen count 10
1943 pollen count 48

10/1/44—Feeling better this year than previously even with starting the tablets after the symptoms had started. Also did not take the tables regularly. 1944 pollen count 3
1943 pollen count 2*
*incomplete count due to showers.

Clinical Summary

9/20/44—Nasal mucosa less congested than at any previous examination; respiratory space fair; post nasal mucoid discharge, slight.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever?
15 years.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? No.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tables? Sept. 1, 1944.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms?
Aug. 14, 1944.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - less
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning?
3 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same No increase
 - b. better
 results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help A little.
 - b. helpful
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? Yes.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Yes.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? No.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? A little.

Remarks: I was at the White Mts. for 3 weeks and had a few light attacks in the morning, but have had 2 bad attacks since returning.

Name: M. M.

Occupation: Salesman.

J. M.

73 Avenue

Flushing, L. I.

Age 35

History

Hay fever for about 24 years. No food allergies, but asthmatic attacks with hay fever symptoms.

Nasal Examination

Negative.

Therapy

1/1/44—Started C.B. pills, 1
T.I.D. First hay fever 1944 pollen count 106
symptoms Aug. 15th. 1943 pollen count 235

Patient did not return to office but reported by phone that she has felt much better this season than in any previous season. Increased dosage from 1 to 2 T.I.D. Increasing dosage seems to be more helpful, but caused some gastric upset for a few days; also an increase in urine.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN
ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 1921.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? No.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Yes.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets?
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? Aug. 15.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse X
 - b. same
 - c. less
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better X
 results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful X
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? A little upset first few days.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Yes.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? Some years ago, 1937.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? No.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Name J. M.

Occupation: Housewife.

Case XVI

G. E. P.

935 St. Nicholas Avenue

New York, New York Age 38

History

5/1/44—Nasal obstruction and discharge with sneezing and rhinitis since November and December. Headaches at times. Has used vaso constrictor. Tickling in throat. No ear com-

plaints except stuffiness. Has wheezing in chest. No family history of hay fever or asthma. All other negative.

Examination

Mucosa —Hyperplastic, engorged, allergic in type.
Septum —In mid position.
Turbinates—Polypoid changes in right middle turbinate.
Throat —Buccal mucosa normal.
Tonsils —Removed.
Pharynx —Negative.
Larynx —Negative.
Drum —Show slight retraction.

Therapy

5/1/44 —Examination—Allergy testing
milk + feathers 1+
eggs 3+ dust 4+
chocolate 2+ timothy 1+
ragweed 1+

5/3/44 —Started injections concentrated dust and respiratory UBA.

7/24/44—Sub mucous resection at office.

8/1/44 —C.B. pills, started 2 1944 pollen count 0
T.I.D. 1943 pollen count 0

8/11/44—H.P. 7.0. 1944 pollen count 26
1943 pollen count 27

8/24/44—C.B. pills, started 3 1944 pollen count 110
T.I.D. 1943 pollen count 110

9/4/44 —States of slight irritation of stomach. Otherwise less sneezing than in 1944 pollen count 238
previous years. 1943 pollen count 45

10/1/44—No sneezing. Better than in previous 1944 pollen count 3
years 1943 pollen count 2*
*incomplete count due to showers

Clinical Summary

8/11/44—Both inferior turbinates engorged; partial nasal obstruction; mucoid nasal discharge.

8/24/44—Inferior turbinates less congested; fair amount of nasal space; diminished mucoid discharge.

10/1/44—Nasal mucosa appears quite normal; excellent nasal space; inferior turbinates appear normal; nasal discharge within normal range.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN
ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 2 years.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Slight year round.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? August.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? All year.

- 6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less X
 than previous years?
- 7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 6 daily then 9 daily.
- 8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better X
 results?
- 9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful X
- 10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? Slight.
- 11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
- 12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better X
 than previous years?
- 13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
- 14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Never had any.
- 15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Remarks: Improvement better over previous years, but I did not have medical treatment before for same.
 Name: G. E. P.
 Occupation: Trained Nurse.

Case XVII

R. R.
 135-48 77th Ave.
 Flushing, New York Age 6

History

Had hives at age of 3 with patches on chest but no nasal symptoms. At 4, developed sneezing and rhinitis in August and September. Has been treated and found sensitive to cauliflower, wheat, beef, grapes, strawberry, rice, spinach, pineapple, beets, lettuce, tomato, salmon, string beans, wool and dust. Not much hives now.

Operations—none. Mumps at 18 months.
 Hereditary—Father gets occasional hives.

Examination

Sinuses—negative.

Therapy

6/17/44—Allergic testing
 dust 4+ milk 4+
 feathers 4+ egg white 4+
 chocolate 4+ ragweed 4+

C.B. pills started T.I.D.

6/30/44—Patient appears the same.

7/1/44 —C.B. pills stopped. Not much relieved. Taking nucleic acid powder instead with relief.

Clinical Summary

6/30/44—Nasal mucosa congested and engorged; slight amount mucoid discharge; nasal space fair.

7/1/44 —Nasal mucosa engorged; slight mucoid discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

- 1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 2 years.
- 2. Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.
- 3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
- 4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? July, 1944.
- 5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? August.
- 6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less X
 than previous years?
- 7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 daily.
- 8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same No increase.
 - b. better
 results?
- 9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help X
 - b. helpful
- 10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No
- 11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
- 12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better X
 than previous years?
- 13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
- 14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? No.
- 15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? No.

Remarks: Vitamin C tablets stopped after 2 weeks. Now taking Nucleic Acid powder with relief.
 Name: R. R.
 Occupation: Child 6 years.

Case XVIII

S. R.
 240 West 73rd Street
 New York, N. Y. Old patient

History

P.C.—Had plastic four years ago. For last year he has had sneezing and running nose, but has had no relief. Occasional headache. Hay fever for 17 years. Asthmatic attacks occasionally in hay fever season.

Examination

Patient has had a nasal plastic with partial collapse of both nasal alae.
 Mucosa —Hyperplastic and engorged.
 Turbinates—Inferior turbinates hypertrophied.

Discharge—Serous nasal discharge; redness and excoriation of both nasal alae.

Therapy

- 4/14/44 —Allergy testing 4+ to dust and feathers.
 4/19/44 —Series of Canc. Dust and Resp. Injections started.
 6/2/44 —Started Vitamin C tablets, 1 T.I.D.
 6/28/44 —Increased to 2 T.I.D.
 7/1/44 —Increased to 3 T.I.D.
 8/7/44 —Sneezing decreased.
 Feeling of digestive disturbances. In- 1944 pollen count 4
 creased diaphoresis. 1943 pollen count 6
 8/28/44 —Slight increase of
 urine, otherwise
 less sneezing than 1944 pollen count 56*
 previously. 1943 pollen count 98
 9/21/44 }—Did not take the Vitamin C during this
 } period and sneezed more than at the time
 9/28/44 }—she was taking them.
 * Incomplete due to showers.

Clinical Summary

- 6/2/44 —Nasal mucosa markedly congested; very little nasal space; serous nasal discharge.
 6/28/44—Moderate nasal congestion; nasal fossae show fair degree of space; slight mucoid discharge.
 8/7/44 —Nasal mucosa slightly congested; good nasal space; slight mucoid discharge.
 8/28/44—Good nasal passageway; mucosa appears fairly normal; slight mucoid discharge.
 9/21/44—Good nasal space; nasal mucosa appears fairly normal.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

- For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 17.
- Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.
- Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Occasionally.
- When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? June, 1944.
- When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? Aug. 18, 1944.
- Would you consider your attacks
 - worse
 - same
 - less X
 than previous years?
- How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 a day., subsequently 9 a day—altogether 400 tablets.
- Did increasing the dosage give
 - same
 - better X
 results?
- Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - no help
 - helpful X
- Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? Once in a while.
- Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Yes.
- Did you feel generally
 - same
 - worse
 - better X
 than previous years?
- Did you also receive hay fever injections? Yes.
- Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Yes.
- Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks. Yes.
 Remarks: Did not take the pills from Sept. 21st to Sept. 28th and missed them and sneezed during that period.
 Name: S. H. Occupation: Saleslady.
 A. R.
 532 W. 143rd Street
 New York, N. Y.

History

About five years ago had nasal obstruction. Occasional headache. Last August had hay fever. Frontal headaches. Eyes feel heavy, feel tired. Has trouble with menses. History of hay fever for thirteen years. No allergies to food.

Examination

Mucosa—Vasomotor rhinitis.
 Septum—Moderately deflected.
 Impacted middle turbinate.
 Bilateral hyperplastic ethmoiditis.

Therapy

- Turbineotomy in 1933
 7/15/44—Started on C.B. pills, 1 T.I.D.
 8/1/44 —Slight increase of
 urination. No irrita- 1944 pollen count 0
 tion of stomach. 1943 pollen count 0
 8/15/44—C.B. pills increased 1944 pollen count 32
 to 3 T.I.D. 1943 pollen count 25
 9/1/44—Increase in urination. Otherwise feeling fine
 with very little sneezing.

Clinical Summary

- 8/1/44 —Nasal mucosa slightly engorged; very little nasal discharge; moderate nasal obstruction.
 8/15/44—Nasal fossae show good space; mucosa not engorged; very little nasal discharge.
 9/1/44 —Nasal mucosa hyperplastic, but shows no vasomotor disturbances; nasal fossae fairly clear; very little nasal discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

- For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 13 years.
- Do you have food allergies as well? No.
- Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.

4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? Middle of July.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? End of August.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same X
 - c. less
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better X
 results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful X
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Yes.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better X
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Never took any.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Remarks: Due to a bad season I was not as well as the past two years.

Name: J. C.

Occupation: Actress.

E. S.

Flushing, L. I.

Age 40

History

Hay fever for past twenty years. No food allergies.

Examination

Vasomotor rhinitis.

Therapy

9/2/44—Started C.B. pills, 3 T.I.D. First hay fever symptoms August 15th 1944 pollen count 346 1943 pollen count 233 Patient did not return to office for further treatment but reported by phone that she is feeling much better than she had in previous years while she was taking hay fever injections. None given this year. The C.B. pills seem to modify her attacks a great deal. No irritation of stomach or bladder reported.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? About 20.

2. Do you have food allergies as well? No.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? Sept.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? Aug. 15.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. less X
 than previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 9 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better
 results?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful X
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better X
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? Yes.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Yes.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Name: E. S.

Occupation: Housewife.

F. B. S.

2214 64th Street

Brooklyn, N. Y.

Age 26

History

Has had hay fever for last 4 years. About 2 weeks ago had nasal obstruction. Has nasal stuffiness, sneezing and running. Had 6 injections of hydrochloric acid for hay fever. Operations—Thyroidectomy 12 years ago.

Examination

Septum —Deflected sharply to the left.
 Turbinates —Inferior turbinates hypertrophied.
 Mucosa —Hyperplastic—nasal fossae markedly obstructed.
 Discharge —Mucoïd discharge both middle meati—serous mucoïd discharge.
 Transillumination—Moderately diminished both sides.
 Tonsils —Removed.

Therapy

6/3/44 —Started hay fever injections. Started C.B. Pills, 1 T.I.D.

- 8/15/44—Increase in urination.
Slight irritation of stomach. 1944 pollen count 32
1943 pollen count 25
- 9/3/44 —First hay fever symptom with very little sneezing. Increased dosage to 3 T.I.D. 1944 pollen count 354
1943 pollen count 106*
- 9/15/44—Feels better this year than previously; instead of losing weight, patient gained 4 pounds; very little sneezing. 1944 pollen count 75
1943 pollen count 51
*incomplete count due to showers.

Clinical Summary

- 8/15/44—Nasal mucosa not engorged; moderately good nasal space; very little nasal discharge.
- 9/3/44 —Nasal engorgement of the mucosa, moderate, with fair nasal space and slight sero-mucinous discharge.
- 9/15/44—Nasal fossae shows good ventilation; mucosa not engorged; very little nasal discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

- For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 8.
- Do you have food allergies as well? No.
- Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
- When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? May 15th.
- When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? August.
- Would you consider your attacks
 - worse
 - same
 - less
 than previous years?
- How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 a day, then increased to 6, then 9 a day.
- Did increasing the dosage give
 - same
 - better
 results?
- Do you think the Special Vitamin C Tablets were
 - no help
 - helpful Very.
- Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
- Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Yes.
- Did you feel generally
 - same
 - worse
 - better
 than previous years?
- Did you also receive hay fever injections? Yes.
- Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Not much.

- Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Remarks: This year the hay fever attacks started later than any previous year, namely Sept. 3rd. Also, instead of losing weight during the season, I gained about 4 lbs.

Name: F. B. S.

Occupation: Housewife.

Case XXII

P. S.

140 Riverside Drive

New York, New York Age 45

History

9/10/43—Sneezing for last two weeks. No previous attacks. Has frontal headache, nasal obstruction. Has itching of eyes. No sore throat.

Examination.

Mucosa—Allergic type — bilateral hyperplastic pansinusitis.

Septum—Moderately deflected.

Tonsils —Removed.

Therapy

6/7/44 —Started hay fever injections but discontinued before the series was completed as patient did not come in for injections as scheduled.

8/5/44 —Started C.B. pills 3 1944 pollen count 0
T.I.D. 1943 pollen count 0

9/15/44—Patient took only a few, perhaps 3 dozen C.B. pills but then not every day. Unable to judge if they were of any help or not. 1944 pollen count 75
1943 pollen count 51

Clinical Summary

8/5/44 —Nasal mucosa moderately congested; nasal fossae partially obstructed; fairly profuse serous discharge; nasal alae reddened and slightly excoriated.

9/15/44—Nasal mucosa still congested; nasal ventilation poor; sero-mucinous discharge.

9/4/44 —Nasal mucosa congested; nasal fossae partially obstructed; moderate serous discharge.

9/25/44—Nasal mucosa moderately engorged; nasal fossae show moderate nasal obstruction; moderate serous discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

- For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 7 years.
- Do you have food allergies as well? No.
- Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Yes.
- When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? Aug. 1.
- When did you first have any hay fever symptoms?

6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse X
 - b. same
 - c. less
 than previous years?
 7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 9 a day.
 8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. better
 results?
 9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C Tablets were
 - a. no help X
 - b. helpful
 10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? Don't know.
 11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
 12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse X
 - c. better
 than previous years?
 13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? Yes.
 14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Yes.
 15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Not much.
- Remarks: I took only a few of the tablets.
Name: P. S.
Occupation: Dress Manufacturer.

Case XXIII

S. A. S.
275 Central Park West
New York, New York

History

Hay fever for 4 or 5 years.

Examination

Mucosa —Nasal Mucosa moderately hypertrophic.
Buccal mucosa is normal.

Septum —In midline.

Turbinates—Inferior turbinates moderately hypertrophic on both sides.

Tongue —Slightly coated.

Tonsils —Removed, adenoids removed. At the orifice of the right Eustachian tube is some small papillomatous tissue.

Right Ear—Large drum defect occupying posterior half of drum membrane, now healed by scar adherent to the promontory and to the head of the stapes.

Left Ear —Large healed central perforation with calcification of upper portion of drum membrane and retraction.

Therapy

8/1/44 —Allergy testing with
4+ Ragweed and
Timothy. Started on 1944 pollen count 0
C.B. pills, 2 T.I.D. 1943 pollen count 0

9/4/44 —Some sneezing. Dosage increased to 3 T.I.D. No increase

in urine or stomach 1944 pollen count 238
irritation. 1943 pollen count 45

9/25/44—Still sneezing. Patient explains this as due to being exposed more to pollen this year due 1944 pollen count 9
to military activities. 1943 pollen count 4

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 4 or 5 years.
 2. Do you have food allergies as well? Don't know.
 3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Yes.
 4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? August.
 5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? 5 years ago.
 6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same X
 - c. less
 than previous years?
 7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 6 daily.
 8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same X
 - b. better
 results?
 9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help X
 - b. helpful
 10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
 11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
 12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same X
 - b. worse
 - c. better
 than previous years?
 13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
 14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Did not have any.
 15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? No.
- Remarks: I was more exposed to pollen this year because of military training.
Name: S. A. S.
Occupation: Attorney.

Case XXIV

K. T.
44 Metropolitan Oval
New York, N. Y. Age 26

History

Allergic from August to end of hay fever season. Post nasal drip. Occasional headaches. Also has hives.

Examination

Mucosa —Hyperplastic.
Septum —Deflected to right.

Buccal mucosa—Normal.
Teeth —Calcium deficiency.
Tongue —Mucosa thickened.
Tonsils —Removed.
Ears —Negative.

Therapy

7/25/44—Allergy testing 4+ to Ragweed and Timothy.
8/7/44 —Started C.B. pills, 1 1944 pollen count 4
T.I.D. 1943 pollen count 6
8/20/44—First hay fever symptoms with very little sneezing. Increased dosage to 3 T.I.D. 1944 pollen count 40
1943 pollen count 66
9/1/44—Slight increase in urination. 1944 pollen count 106
1943 pollen count 235
9/10/44—No sneezing after increase of dosage. Much better this season than previously. 1944 pollen count 50
1943 pollen count 32

Clinical Summary

8/20/44—Moderate nasal engorgement; moderate nasal obstruction; increased mucoid discharge.
9/1/44 —Less nasal obstruction; mucosa slightly engorged; slight mucoid discharge.
9/10/44—Fair nasal space; slight mucosal congestion and slight mucoid discharge.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

- For how many seasons have you had hay fever? 15.
- Do you have food allergies as well? Yes, slightly.
- Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
- When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? August 7.
- When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? August 20.
- Would you consider your attacks
 - worse
 - same X
 - less
 than previous years?
- How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 a day.
- Did increasing the dosage give
 - same
 - better X
 results?
- Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - no help
 - helpful X
- Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
- Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Yes.
- Did you feel generally
 - same
 - worse
 - better X
 than previous years?

- Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
- Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? No.
- Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.
Name: K. T.
Occupation: Secretary.

M. O. 117-01 Park Lane S.
Kew Gardens, N. Y. Age 3

History

Since the beginning of August has been having nasal obstruction, sneezing and nasal discharge, particularly bad at night and disturbing the baby's sleep.

Examination

Mucosa —Swollen, occluding almost completely both nasal fossae.
Turbinates—Inferior turbinates in contact with septum on both sides.
Tonsils —Hypertrophied and diseased.

Therapy

9/6/44 —Child came to office with typical hay fever symptoms. Sneezing, running eyes and nose. Tested for ragweed 4+ results. Has had symptoms since 8/20/44. Started with C.B. pills, 1944 pollen count 312
2 T.I.D. 1943 pollen count 60
9/20/44—Very little sneezing. Nose and eyes not running. Child greatly relieved by the C.B. pills. 1944 pollen count 10
1943 pollen count 48

Clinical Summary

9/20/44—Nasal passageway clear; very little nasal discharge; inferior turbinates appear normal.

B. W.

734 E. 6th Street
New York, N. Y. Age 27

History

Hay fever; post nasal discharge. Hay fever for the past fifteen years, very severe during the last few seasons. Has been unable to work regularly for a number of years during the hay fever season. Recurrent frontal headaches.

Examination

Mucosa —Hyperplastic.
Turbinates—Hypertrophied, both middle turbinates have been partially resected, and a partial anterior ethmoidectomy has been performed.
Septum —In mid position.
Tonsils —Removed.

Therapy

7/20/44—Started ragweed injections.

8/22/44—Started C.B. pills, 2 T.I.D. Allergy testing: ragweed 4+, dust 2+, timothy 4+, feathers 2+. Also some food allergies. 1944 pollen count 93
1943 pollen count 32

8/31/44—Very little sneezing. Increased dosage to 3 T.I.D. 1944 pollen count 131
1943 pollen count 236

9/6/44 —Feeling better than at any other time. States of slight increase in urination. 1944 pollen count 312
1943 pollen count 60

Clinical Summary

8/22/44—Nasal mucosa acutely congested; profuse serous discharge; severe nasal obstruction.

8/31/44—Nasal mucosa slightly congested; nasal fossae fairly clear; very little nasal discharge.

9/6/44 —Nasal fossae show good space; inferior turbinates not congested; nasal mucosa not engorged.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? Two.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? Yes.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? No.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? Aug. 22.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? 2 years ago.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. lessthan previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 a day. Subsequently 6 a day, altogether 300 tablets.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. betterresults?
9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? Yes.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. betterthan previous years?

13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? Yes, before Vitamin C tablets.

14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? Yes.

15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Remarks: Also received dust injections.

Name: B. W.

Occupation: Printing and binding.

M. W.

Mt. Vernon, New York Age 46

History

Has had severe hay fever for last twenty-five years. Has received pollen injection for desensitization for last fifteen years with little benefit. Went to New York Hospital for injections.

Examination

Mucosa —Chronically thickened and hyperplastic—septal mucosa hypertrophied.

Turbinates—Both middle and inferior turbinates hypertrophied.

Septum —In mid position.

Tonsils —Removed

Therapy

7/15/44—Started C.B. pills, 1 T.I.D.

Patient did not return to office but reported by letter that she has felt better this season for the first time in 25 years. Her first symptoms on August 25th; during this season she had only about 4 or 5 very bad attacks but with no asthmatic attacks. States of no irritation to stomach or bladder. Dosage increased in 1 month's time to 2 T.I.D.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON VITAMIN C IN ALLERGY

1. For how many seasons have you had hay fever? About 25 years.
2. Do you have food allergies as well? No.
3. Do you have asthmatic attacks during the hay fever season? Sometimes.
4. When did you start taking the Special Vitamin C tablets? July 15, 1944.
5. When did you first have any hay fever symptoms? On or about August 25, 1944.
6. Would you consider your attacks
 - a. worse
 - b. same
 - c. lessthan previous years?
7. How many tablets did you take at the beginning? 3 a day, then 6 a day.
8. Did increasing the dosage give
 - a. same
 - b. betterresults?

9. Do you think the Special Vitamin C tablets were
 - a. no help
 - b. helpful X
10. Did the tablets cause any irritation of the stomach? No.
11. Was there any increase in urination after taking tablets aside from hay fever symptoms? No.
12. Did you feel generally
 - a. same
 - b. worse
 - c. better X
 than previous years?
13. Did you also receive hay fever injections? No.
14. Have hay fever injections been helpful in previous years? No.
15. Would you consider the Vitamin C tablets modified your hay fever attacks? Yes.

Remarks: I have only had about 4 or 5 very bad attacks this season due to the Vitamin C tablets. I must emphasize the fact that I felt better this season, for the first time in 25 years.

Name: M. W.

Occupation: Housewife.

A supplement of these clinical results is presented with the tabulation of the results obtained in one hundred cases of the common cold and vasomotor rhinitis. In view of frequent association of nasal pathology with nasal allergy, the benefit derived from the calcium cevitamate assumes a double significance, and emphasizes the therapeutic value of vitamin C in large doses. In this latter group on one hundred cases employing calcium ascorbate instead of the vitamin CB tablets as previously described, the therapeutic effect can be attributed essentially to the vitamin C since calcium gluconate has not been shown to be of any value in either the common cold or allergic rhinitis. The antihistamine effect of calcium ascorbate is however, somewhat higher than vitamin C alone.

The great prevalence of allergy prompts us to inquire into the possible etiologic features of this disturbance. It has been well established that allergy is a biochemical derangement intimately related to histamine balance. Today we realize that in these biochemical disturbances nutritional deficiencies both in amino acids and vitamins plays a very significant if not dominant role. In the light of the demonstrated antihistamine effect of vitamin C, it behooves us to consider the widespread distribution of vitamin C deficiency.

Crane, Woods, Waters and Murphy determined the level of ascorbic acid in the blood plasma of eighty-six rural children in grade schools in a northern Maine village in the autumn and again in the spring. The plasma of only two of the eighty-six children contained as much as 0.8 mg. per cent of ascorbic acid in both seasons and dietary studies indicated that probably not more than one child in seven was eating a good source of vitamin C a day. In the autumn the ascorbic acid content of the plasma of 28 per cent of the children was below 0.4 mg. per cent; in the spring 55 per cent were in this category. An association between low ascorbic acid in plasma and an inflammation of the

gums was observed. In the autumn 29 per cent of the children had inflamed gums but by spring the condition had grown worse and 51 per cent had inflamed gums. Administration of ascorbic acid to 41 of the children with inflamed gums indicated that insufficiency of vitamin C probably was a factor in this condition; improvement followed within three weeks in the case of two-thirds of the children treated.

Under the auspices of the Rockefeller Foundation, studies of nutritional status are being made in two rural communities in the South. One was undertaken in 1940 in a rural mill town in North Carolina, in co-operation with the Health Department and Duke University. The other, in co-operation with Vanderbilt University, was begun the year before in a rural area of Tennessee. At the 18th annual conference of the Milbank Memorial Fund Youmans reported findings from the first 129 families studied in the latter investigation. Twenty-five per cent of 411 persons examined in a visual dark adaptation test gave values regarded as definitely abnormal, indicative of vitamin A deficiency; 11 per cent of 502 persons tested had less than 0.3 mg. ascorbic acid per 100 ml. blood plasma, values considered to be unquestionably abnormal; and 26 per cent of 498 individuals examined had lower hemoglobin and 44 per cent lower red cell counts, than current minimum normal values for the sex and age groups studied. Evidence of protein deficiency was noted in 20 per cent of 455 individuals. Though incomplete and preliminary, these data indicate that a large proportion of the population included in the study is poorly nourished with respect to a number of essential nutrients. In addition to the cases noted above as definitely abnormal, an even larger proportion was regarded as border-line, probably subnormal, cases.

Minot and co-workers, in determining the ascorbic acid content of the serum of "normal" children (patients without serious or significant disease attending the pediatric clinic of Vanderbilt hospital), found that about half of those examined in the age range three to fifteen years had ascorbic acid values of 0.7 mg. or more per 100 ml. of serum. These values were considered indicative of a fairly satisfactory state of vitamin C nutrition. However, of the entire group of 380 children under fifteen years of age examined, about 35 per cent of those tested during the winter and about 20 per cent tested during the summer had ascorbic acid values under 0.3 mg. per 100 ml. of blood serum; these values are considered indicative of serious deficiency. Less seasonal variation in values was found among children under three years of age than among those from three to fifteen years, a fact explained by the lesser variation in diets of the younger children. Relatively more sick than well children were found with serum low in ascorbic acid. Although the ascorbic acid levels of many children were low enough to be associated with a marked degree of deficiency of vitamin C in the tissues, a diagnosis of scurvy was rarely made, notwithstanding careful study of roentgenograms and a search for other clinical evidence. Clinical scurvy was not found even among children whose ascorbic acid levels were known to remain persistently below

Name	Sex	Age	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	Remarks
23. F. B.	F	8	no	no		5th	8th	c	3 6 9	b	b	no	yes	c	yes	not much	yes	Combined with desensitization
24. K. T.	F	15	yes	no		8th	8th	b	3	b	b	No	yes	c	no	no	yes	C. B. Pills only
25. M. U.	F	1	yes	?		9th	8th	1st Sea- son	2	no in- crease	b	no	yes	1st Sea-	no	no	yes	C B Pills only
26. B. W.	F	2	yes	no		8th	?	c	3 6	b	b	no	yes	c	yes	yes	yes	Combined with desensitization
27. F. W.	F	25	no	yes		7th 1944	8th 1944	c	3 6	b	b	no	no	c	no	no	yes	C. B. Pills only

Calcium Cevitamate In Acute Rhinitis

Case No.	Pat-ient	Sex	Date	Diagnosis	Comment	Case No.	Pat-ient	Sex	Date	Diagnosis	Comment
1	B. B.	M	3/24, 1937	Acute cold	Marked improvement	18	L.I.M.	M	5/10, 1937	Acute rhinitis	Complete relief
2	C.G.	F	4/5, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief	19	G. B.	F	3/1, 16, 4/6, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
3	E. K.	F	4/5, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief	20	H. C.	F	3/20, 21, 1937	Bilateral maxillary sinusitis	Marked improvement
4	I. G.	F	4/5, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief	21	R. M.	F	3/21, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
5	I. G.	F	4/5, 1937	Acute cold Rt. ethmoiditis	Marked improvement	22	J.O'D.	M	3/20, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
6	H. S.	F	4/1, 2, 5, 7, 1937	Grippe, left sphenoiditis	Marked improvement	23	J. N.	M	3/23, 24, 31, 1937	Bilateral maxillary sinusitis	Marked improvement
7	P. D.	M	4/6, 1937	Aphthous stomatitis. Acute cold	Complete relief. Stomatitis disappeared after one injection.	24	E. S.	F	3/25, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
8	G. B.	M	4/7, 1937	Acute laryngitis	Marked improvement	25	R. G.	F	3/28, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
9	L. G.	F	4/7, 12, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief	26	A. S.	M	10/21, 25, 11/13, 12/21, 1936; 1/15, 29, 2/24, 25, 1937	Acute rhinitis; deflected septum, ethmoid, polypoid	Marked improvement
10	D. S.	F		Bilateral maxillary and ethmoidal sinusitis	Improvement noted with each injection.	27	C. R.	F	10/22, 11/12, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Completely relieved
11	L. K.	M	11/9, 11, 1936	Acute rhinitis Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement	28	H. R.	M	10/23, 26, 11/27, 30, 1936; 1/8, 18, 22, 29, 2/24, 1937	Acute rhinitis Bilateral maxillary ethmoidal sinusitis.	Acute symptoms relieved Sinusitis improved
12	P. S.	F	11/10, 15, 12/7, 1936, 3/31, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement	29	N. K.	F	10/30, 11/2, 4, 6, 11, 12/19, 1936	Vasomotor rhinitis, severe	Marked improvement
13	W. H.	M	4/20, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief	30	E. J.	F	11/2, 9, 13, 17, 1936	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement
14	R. R.	F	4/27, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Moderate improvement.	31	S.W.	F	11/2, 1936	Acute cold	Complete relief
15	F. G.	F	4/27, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement	32	W.J.R.	M	11/3, 9, 23, 1936	Acute rhinitis Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement
16	D.D.D.	M	4/28, 1937	Acute rhinitis	Marked improvement	33	A. S.	F	11/3, 9, 11,	Deflected septum, Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement
17	M. B.	F	5/3, 7, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement						

<i>Case Pat- No. icnt</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Diagnosis</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Case Pat- No. icnt</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Diagnosis</i>	<i>Comment</i>
34 S. T.	F	10/29, 11/3, 10, 25, 1936	Bilateral ethmoiditis; sphenopalatine ganglion neuralgia	Marked improvement	53 C. S.	M	10/26, 28, 1936	Acute cold, Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement
35 G. F.	M	11/4, 1936	Acute cold	Complete relief	54 S. C.	F	10/26, 11/9, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Marked improvement
36 A. G.	M	11/4, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Complete relief	55 R. S.	F	10/27, 30, 1936	Acute cold Hypertrophic turbinates	Marked improvement
37 S. R.	M	10/16, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Relieved completely	56 M. R.	F	10/27, 1936	Acute cold	Marked improvement
38 S. H.	M	10/15, 23, 26, 1936; 1/8, 3/10, 12, 1937	Acute rhinitis, Bilateral ethmoiditis	Relieved completely	57 B. B.	F	10/18, 1936	Acute cold	Complete relief
39 E. L.	M	10/20, 1936	Acute rhinitis Left ethmoiditis	Marked improvement	58 Mr. G.	M	10/28, 1936	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement
40 T. C.	F	10/20, 23, 27, 11/9, 17, 12/9, 13, 21, 1936; 1/5, 8, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement	59 B. N.	M	10/28, 11/2, 9, 23, 12/7, 21, 1936; 1/4, 15, 1937	Acute rhinitis	Complete relief
41 L. A.	F	10/20, 23, 26, 11/7, 12/11, 1936; 2/27, 1937	Acute rhinitis, deviated septum, bilateral ethmoiditis	Relieved of acute attacks. Sinusitis improved.	60 F. W.	M	4/1, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
42 F. R.	F	10/10, 21, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Relieved completely	61 L. L.	M	4/9, 1937	Vasomotor Rhinitis	Marked improvement
43 A. C.	M	10/21, 24, 26, 11/6, 9, 11, 12, 1936	Acute rhinitis, Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement	62 H. W.	M	4/9, 12, 19, 1937	Acute cold	Marked improvement
44 F. S.	M	10/21, 25, 28, 12/14, 1936; 1/27, 3/10, 12, 4/7, 1937	Acute rhinitis, left pan-sinusitis; left radical pan-sinus operation four years ago	Marked improvement	63 A. C.	F	4/10, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis Acute rhinitis	Marked improvement
45 I. E.	M	10/21, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Relieved completely	64 M. R.	F	4/10, 13, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
46 E. E.	F	10/21, 26, 11/4, 1936	Acute rhinitis, Bilateral ethmoiditis	Completely relieved	65 R. M.	M	4/3, 1937	Acute cold	Improved after one injection
47 L. C.	F	10/22, 26, 29, 11/23, 27, 1936	Acute rhinitis, Bilateral ethmoiditis	Completely relieved	66 R. L.	F	4/5, 15, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked improvement
48 J. W.	M	11/9, 12, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Marked improvement	67 D. L.	M	4/13, 1937	Acute rhinitis	Marked improvement
49 A. F.	F	10/23, 26, 11/17, 23, 1936	Acute rhinitis Nasal allergy	Marked improvement	68 K. M.	M	4/13, 1937	Acute rhinitis	Complete relief
50 A. K.	F	10/26, 1936	Acute rhinitis, Bilateral ethmoiditis, left sphenoiditis	Marked relief	69 N. F.	F	4/11, 13, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
51 B. S.	F	10/26, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Completely relieved	70 S.L.R.	M	4/19, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
52 L. S.	F	10/26, 1936	Acute rhinitis right maxillary sinusitis, old radical operation	Marked improvement	71 S. F.	M	4/1, 19, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
					72 M. H.	M	4/19, 23, 27, 30	Bilateral Polypoid, asthma, Maxillary sinusitis	Marked improvement
					73 G. N.	M	4/24, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Complete relief
					74 E. H.	F	4/26, 29, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief
					75 J. F.	M	8/18, 1937	Allergic rhinitis	Marked improvement

<i>Case Pat- No. ient</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Diagnosis</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Case Pat- No. ient</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Diagnosis</i>	<i>Comment</i>
76 A. B.	F	8/18, 1937	Acute rhinitis Acute otitis, grippe type	Improved. No paracen- tosis	91 I. B.	F	10/28, 11/6, 16, 1936	Deviated sep- tum Bilat- eral eth- moiditis, acute rhinitis	Marked im- provement
77 M. R.	F	6/25, 28, 1937	Acute rhinitis	Complete relief	92 R. T.	M	10/28, 11/2, 16, 1936	Sinusitis; bi- lateral maxil- lary sinusitis. Asthma	Marked im- provement in asthma and sinusitis
78 J. B.	M	10/28, 1937	Acute cold	Complete relief	93 C. N.	M	10/30, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Completely relieved
79 A. S.	M	7/8, 13, 8/16, 1937	Nasal allergy; bilateral max- illary & eth- moidal sinu- sitis	Marked im- provement	94 C. A.	M	10/30, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Completely relieved
80 B. L.	F	7/12, 16, 1937	Acute rhinitis & bronchitis	Marked im- provement	95 A. M.	M	10/31, 11/7, 21, 1936	Allergic vaso- motor rhin- itis	Marked im- provement
81 I. L.	F	7/17, 8/9, 25, 9/16, 20, 24, 27, 10/1, 3, 7, 15, 18, 19, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Moderately improved	96 R. M.	F	11/1, 9, 19, 12/2, 20, 1936, 1/5, 10, 15, 2/19, 25, 3/16, 1937	Post-nasal drip, Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked im- provement
82 L. S.	F	7/17, 23, 8/4, 6, 13, 20, 9/8, 12, 28, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked im- provement	97 D. K.	F	10/14, 20	Allergic rhin- itis, polypoid pan-sinusitis, Deflected septum	Allergy im- proved greatly, sin- usitis re- curred, radi- cal opera- tion
83 L. I.	M	4/9, 1927	Allergic rhinitis	Marked im- provement	98 N. G.	F	7/16, 9/27, 10/25, 1937	Bilateral max- illary sinu- sitis, severe asthma, nasal allergy	Asthma completely relieved, sinusitis markedly improved
84 A. C.	F	4/10, 1937	Bilateral ethmoiditis	Marked im- provement	99 J. S.	F	6/28, 7/14, 10, 20, 23, 1937	Bilateral max- illary ethmoid sinusitis, severe asthma, nasal allergy	Asthma markedly improved, sinusitis markedly improved
85 S. F.	M	4/1, 19, 1937	Acute cold, post-nasal drip	Marked im- provement	100 J. G.	M	8/1, 21, 24, 31, 9/1, 3, 16, 25, 10/2, 9, 16, 25, 30, 1937	Bilateral eth- moiditis, nasal allergy, asthma	Asthma completely relieved, nasal al- lergy re- lieved sinus- itis marked- ly improved
86 R. L.	F	4/5, 17, 1937	Bilateral eth- moiditis, sin- usitis	Moderately improved					
87 F. W.	F	11/7, 1936	Acute cold	Complete relief					
88 L. S.	M	11/7, 9, 1936	Acute cold	Complete relief					
89 M. R.	M	11/7, 1936	Acute cold	Complete relief					
90 O. F.	M	10/28, 1936	Acute rhinitis	Complete relief					

0.2 mg. per 100 ml. of serum. The authors suggest that diets that are simultaneously deficient in calories and several other essential food factors may suppress the typical manifestations of deficiency; such low levels of ascorbic acid in otherwise adequately nourished persons might cause obvious scurvy. The investigators call attention to the lack of energy, poor appetite, mental apathy, and generally retarded development that characterized the children. These symptoms probably reflect not only a shortage of vitamin C, but diets that are inadequate in many respects.

Macy and associates observed that infants who were receiving a limited and constant supply of the vitamin showed no signs of scurvy normally, but when they were subjected to the added stress of minor infections, indications of clinical scurvy appeared. Later the signs of scurvy disappeared spontaneously when the effect of the infection had passed. The frequency of hay fever developing on a background of chronic sinusitis is so common that a relationship can hardly escape observation. A connection between chronic infection, nutritional deficiency and allergy has often been implied and may now be formulated.

In the light of these findings, it is possible that where nutritional deficiencies beside that of vitamin C occur, the administration of ascorbic acid alone may not be adequate to achieve proper histamine balance and freedom from allergy. It does not appear that the correction of subclinical vitamin C deficiency may play a very important role in elevating the threshold of allergic sensitivity. From this angle, allergy may be classified among the ever increasing list of nutritional deficiency diseases.

The experimental work undertaken to demonstrate the position of vitamin C among the physiologic forces involved in allergy showed its role as a histamine antagonist. This was accomplished through the microscopic observation of bronchiolar reactions to histamine and antihistamine drugs. As a result of this work, the following scheme was developed. The experiment is described in detail to facilitate future studies by other investigators.

The object of the experiment was to secure a viable section of bronchiole. This was accomplished by fixing the lung of the rabbit in gelatin, chilling it and then cutting a thin section of a bronchiole, which was kept in Ringer-Locke dextrose solution. The section was mounted on a ring so that when the gelatin was dissolved out the reactions of the bronchiole could be observed under the microscope and drawn to size. The whole procedure was conducted with adequate controls to assure the viability of the bronchiolar sections.

I first observed the technic of the microscopic study of bronchiolar reactions in the laboratory of Dr. H. D. Pease, who had constructed an ingenious microscope platform that permitted maintenance of a water bath of constant temperature for the ordinary Petri dish. This could readily be elaborated for a series of microscopes. In general, the technic of Sollmann and Gilbert was used as follows: Each of the following substances was dissolved separately in 500 cc. of water:

	Gm.
Sodium chloride	31.5
Potassium chloride	1.47
Calcium chloride	0.84
Sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO ₃)	1.15

The solutions were mixed and diluted to 3.5 liters. On the day of use, dextrose, 1 gm. per liter, was added. Substances to be tested which are sufficiently soluble that a dilution of 1:50 is adequate are made up in distilled water. Those which are less soluble are made up in Ringer-Locke solution.

The animal was killed by intravenous injection of air. The skin was removed from the ventral portion of the abdomen, the thorax and the neck. A midline incision was made from the middle of the abdomen, to the diaphragm. Lateral incisions were made just posterior to the diaphragm toward the sides of the body.

The diaphragm was punctured on each side, allowing the lungs to collapse. The ventral thoracic wall was removed, longitudinal cuts being made along the sides of the thorax anterior to the first pair of ribs. Care was taken not to cut the large axillary veins. A hemostat should be used on any small vessels which are accidentally cut. The first rib and the episternum were carefully removed, carrying with them the ventral neck muscles. The trachea was cut and a cannula inserted, which was held in place with hemostats. The lungs were filled to approximately normal expansion with gelatin (approximately 15 c. of warm 10 per cent gelatin dissolved in Ringer-Locke solution for each kilogram of body weight). The inferior vena cava was clamped with a hemostat, and the lungs, heart and trachea were removed and placed in ice-cold Ringer-Locke solution (approximately 150 cc.). The organs were placed in the freezing compartment of the refrigerator for one to one and a half hours.

The two large lobes of the lung were trimmed to approximately one-half size and thin sections of tissue cut across the bronchiole. These sections should be as thin as possible (0.5 to 1 mm. in thickness). The sections were placed in the cold Ringer-Locke solution in which the lungs were kept. The sections were

kept ice cold until each one was used.

If the substance to be tested was to be diluted, 49 cc. of Ringer-Locke solution was placed in the special dishes (9 cm. Petri dishes, in the center of which a ring of cork with a central opening, approximately 5 cm. in diameter, was cemented with beeswax). The section to be used was pinned out with the bronchiole over the opening of the cork. The sections should not be stretched but should be pinned out flat. The dish was placed on the warm stage and the contents of the dish allowed to warm to 37 C., the section being agitated by means of a stream of Ringer-Locke solution from a small pipet. Camera lucida drawings of the bronchiolar lumen were made until it was of constant size (this usually took ten to fifteen minutes). The test solution was added near the edge of the Petri dish and mixed with a pipet. Then a small amount of fluid in the dish was picked up with the pipet and allowed to run out gently over the tissue. Camera lucida drawings were made as indicated by the reaction of the bronchiole.

In tests designed to show possible antagonism between two substances it was found that the second substance should generally be added about five minutes after the first. The drawings made for each test were dated and a number assigned to each. Each drawing was labeled with the exact time of day, and later these times were translated into terms of minutes which elapsed after the section was put into the dish. These drawings were filed as a permanent record.

Computation of Results:—The area of the bronchiolar lumen was measured in arbitrary units by means of a polar planimeter. The area just before the addition of the first substances to be tested was taken as 100 per cent, and was called the original area. Reactions were expressed as percentages of this original area which remained.

The animals used were white New Zealand rabbits, partially standardized as to age, weight, health and environment. Five animals were prepared and used as described.

The concentration of the solution was kept equal for all comparative tests. The solution of histamine was made up with 100 mg. of histamine hydrochloride to 100 cc. of Ringer-Locke solution. The dilution factor for all solutions of test substances was 1:50, giving with the histamine solution a 1:50,000 concentration.

Experiments 1 and 2 for each day were made as controls. The experiments were arranged in the order of the days on which they were conducted so that the daily controls could be checked against the day's experiments. For each of five groups a new animal was killed, and the experiments and the controls were run simultaneously.

The purpose of the experiment was to produce contraction of the bronchiole by adding histamine hydrochloride to the Ringer-Locke-dextrose solution to obtain a 1:50,000 concentration. After the contraction due to the histamine was established, and at a fixed interval, the substance to be tested for histamine antagonism was added. Those substances which antagonize histamine allowed the bronchiole to relax and in

some instances continued the dilatation above normal. The control tests also showed that there was a spontaneous tendency for the histamine effect to diminish, with a secondary histamine contraction after about fifteen minutes. As a countercheck for histamine antagonism, therefore, two sets of tests were run. In one series, the substance to be tested was added after the histamine contraction had occurred, and the effect was noted. In the other, histamine contraction was produced, the substance added and the histamine antagonism noted; then histamine was again added to see whether the histamine antagonism of the substance would prevent further histamine effect. With substances having histamine-antagonistic properties, then, there would be no or little contraction of the bronchiole on the secondary addition of histamine. The controls uniformly showed a secondary contraction when the histamine was added for the second time. This double checking system thus provided useful information.

RESULTS OF INVESTIGATION

Group 1—Experiments 1 and 2: These tests were conducted to establish normal as well as histamine controls and a subsequent histamine control after twenty-four minutes. Results for 6 normal and 6 histamine controls were plotted and normal and histamine curves established.

On the day of these experiments the normal control maintained a fairly steady bronchiolar lumen, with only gradual contraction. The histamine control showed rapid contraction of the bronchiole with recovery and a second contraction under the continued action of the histamine, thus causing a secondary drop after seventeen minutes.

Experiments 3 and 4: These tests were conducted with the same tissues as those used in experiments 1 and 2. When sodium ascorbate was added after the histamine recovery was slower than in the control, but the histamine antagonism was evident on the addition of the second dose of histamine hydrochloride after fourteen minutes. There was no secondary histamine contraction.

Experiments 5 and 6: The histamine antagonism of vitamin C alone was evident. Here, again, there was a somewhat slower recovery of the bronchiolar lumen, and recovery was maintained, even after a second dose of histamine, although there was a slight contraction for two minutes.

Summary: The sodium ascorbate and vitamin C did not influence the speed of recovery from histamine contraction but did produce antagonism to the second dose of histamine hydrochloride.

Group 2.—On this day controls showed that the bronchiolar lumen maintained its normal size for the whole thirty minutes. The histamine response was strongly active after thirty minutes, indicating that a secondary histamine contraction was obtainable after exposure for this period.

Experiments 3 and 4: Normal recovery from the effect of histamine hydrochloride was slightly inhibited by ephedrine sulfate, indicating that the drug had a slight constricting action on the bronchiole, with little

or no antagonism to the second dose of histamine.

Experiments 5 and 6: Ephedrine ascorbate produced prompt recovery from a sharper histamine contraction than that showed in the control with maintenance of a good level of histamine antagonism after the second dose.

Experiments 7 and 8: With ephedrine hydrochloride there was a decidedly increased histamine contraction as compared with the response with either ephedrine ascorbate or ephedrine sulfate, as well as delayed recovery. Ephedrine hydrochloride is therefore a bronchiole constricting agent with no histamine antagonism.

Summary: Ephedrine sulfate caused slight inhibition of recovery from histamine hydrochloride, with little or no antagonism to the second dose of histamine. With ephedrine ascorbate there was quick recovery from histamine and fair antagonism to the second dose of histamine. With ephedrine hydrochloride there was an increase in histamine contraction and no histamine antagonism, rather constriction.

Group 3.—Controls for this day showed normal maintenance of the bronchiolar lumen for thirty minutes and an active secondary response to histamine hydrochloride after thirty minutes.

Experiments 3 and 4: Experiments conducted with calcium ascorbate showed a sharp recovery after the first histamine contraction, followed by a moderate drop and a moderate rise after the second dose of histamine. This was more rapid than the response with either vitamin C alone or sodium ascorbate.

Experiments 5 and 6: Calcium gluconate showed no histamine antagonism; in fact, it prolonged the action of the drug. The bronchiole did not recover from the histamine contraction for the whole thirty minutes.

Summary: Calcium gluconate not only did not antagonize histamine hydrochloride, but, in fact, increased contraction of the bronchiole to the drug. Calcium ascorbate, on the other hand, antagonized histamine, and the response was quicker than that to either vitamin C alone or sodium ascorbate. This is significant in view of the conflicting claims made for calcium in the treatment of asthma. It appears from this experiment that the synergistic effect of vitamin C on calcium may be the all-deciding factor in the therapeutic value of calcium in allergy. In fact, calcium gluconate may produce unfavorable results in the treatment of asthma, while calcium ascorbate may be useful.

Group 4.—Controls on this day showed fairly normal maintenance of the bronchiolar lumen, as well as a prompt response to a second dose of histamine hydrochloride after twenty-seven minutes.

Experiments 3 and 4: The histamine antagonism of benzedrine ascorbate was followed by active dilatation of the bronchiole. That this dilatation was active was demonstrated by a secondary response to histamine, although the secondary contraction brought the lumen to only a little below normal, and well above the initial histamine contraction.

Experiments 5 and 6: These tests were all the more interesting because benzedrine sulfate gave no such response as did benzedrine ascorbate; in fact, it prolonged histamine contraction and produced virtually no histamine block. Benzedrine sulfate may be considered as bronchiole constricting.

SUMMARY

In this group of experiments a remarkable difference in pharmacologic action is evident. While benzedrine ascorbate produced a quick recovery from histamine contraction, with strong histamine block, the benzedrine sulfate showed no histamine antagonism, and in fact prolonged histamine contraction. The implications of this experiment may be important in relation to histamine shock. While benzedrine sulfate can keep a soldier alert, it may predispose him to greater histamine shock, whereas the vitamin C salt may protect against histamine shock.

Group 5.—Experiments 1 and 2: The bronchiole used in these controls was sensitive and reacted strongly to histamine, with poor spontaneous recovery; after twenty-one minutes the bronchiole responded with sharp contraction to histamine. The spontaneous recovery from histamine was only about 44 per cent.

Experiments 3 and 4: Epinephrine ascorbate produced immediate recovery from histamine, with such strong histamine antagonism that the second dose of histamine hydrochloride did not prevent continuation of the bronchiolar dilatation to over twice the normal size.

Experiments 5 and 6: Epinephrine hydrochloride, as was to be expected, produced active recovery from histamine contraction, with moderate dilatation of the bronchiole.

Summary: One is struck by the remarkable synergistic effect of vitamin C on epinephrine. The epinephrine ascorbate showed about twice the bronchiole-dilating capacity exerted by epinephrine hydrochloride and a much quicker and more active histamine antagonism.

CONCLUSIONS

As a result of these studies several broad conclusions can be arrived at.

First, vitamin C plays a valuable role in the treatment of nasal allergy, but is useful fundamentally in large doses ranging from a minimum of 250 mg. daily with an optimum dosage of 750 mg. daily.

Second, that vitamin C is useful in allergy either by oral therapy or by injection.

Third, the results of the administration of vitamin C are in general advantageous to allergic patients with or without desensitization.

Fourth, in some cases vitamin C therapy alone proved superior to pollen desensitization in previous years.

Fifth, allergic disturbances are related to nutritional deficiencies, primarily that of ascorbic acid.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Abbasy, M. A.; Harris, L. J., and Ellman, P.; Excretion of Vitamin C in Pulmonary Tuberculosis and in Rheumatoid Arthritis, *Lancet* 2:181, 1937.
2. Abt, Arthur F.: The Detoxifying Action of Vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid) in Arsenical Therapy. *J. A. M. A.*, 1692 Nov. 15, 1941.
3. Archer, H. E. and Graham, G.: On the Excretion of Ascorbic Acid, *Lancet* 1:710, 1936; Subscurvey State in Relation to Gastric and Duodenal Ulcer, *ibid.* 20:364, 1936.
4. Aron, Hans, C. S.: The Detoxifying Action of Vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid) in Arsenical Therapy. *J. A. M. A.*, 1692, Nov. 15, 1941.
5. Barlow, O. W.; Beams, A. J.: A Comparison of the Bronchodilating Action of Several Anti-Asthmatic Agents After Anaphylaxis and Histamine Shock in The Guinea Pig. *J. Pharmacol. & Exper. Therap* 47:111, 1933.
6. Biss, E.: Grave Erythroderma Due to Arsphenamine; Cases Cured by Cevitamic Acid, *Rec. med. de la Suisse Rom.*, 58:603, 1938.
7. Bourne, G.: The Effect of Ascorbic Acid (Vitamin C), Calcium Ascorbate, and Calcium Gluconate on the Regeneration of Bone in Rats, *Quart. J. Exper. Physiol.* 31:319, 1942.
8. Bundesen, Herman N.: The Detoxifying Action of Vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid) in Arsenical Therapy. *J. A. M. A.* 1692, Nov. 15, 1941.
9. Cameron, W. M.; Tainer, M. L.: Comparative Actions of Sympathomimetic Compounds: Broncho-Dilator Actions in Bronchial Spasm Induced by Histamine. *J. Pharmacol. & Exer. Therap.* 576:152, 1926.
10. Cormia, F. E. Postarsphenamine Dermatitis: The Relation of Vitamin C to the Production of Arsphenamine Sensitiveness, and Its Use as an Adjunct to Further Arsphenamine Therapy in Patients with Cutaneous Hypersensitiveness to the Arsphenamines. *J. Invest. Dermat.*, 4:81-93, 1941.
11. Co Tui; Burststein, C. L.; Wright, A. M.: The Effect of Sympathectomy on the Sensitivity to Adrenalin of the Bronchioles, *J. Pharmacol. & Exper. Therap.* 58:33, 1936.
12. Dainow, J.: Considerations sur la pathogenic de L'erythrodermie arsenobenzolique: Role de la vitamine C *Ann. de dermat. et syph.*, 10: 139, 1939.
13. Dainow, J.: Use in Reduction of Intolerance in Arsphenamine Used in Therapy of Syphilis: Relations to Avitaminosis to Intolerance Cases. *Presse Med.*, 45:1670-1672, Nov. 24, 1937.
14. Dioconescu, N., Constantinescu, V. and others: Vitamin C in Therapy of Arsphenamine Intolerance. *Rev. san mil, Bucuresti*, 37-627-630, 1938.
15. Falconer, E. H., Epstein, N. N. and Mills, Edith S.: Purpura Hemorrhagic Due to Arsphenamines: Sensitivity in Patients as Influenced by Vitamin C Therapy. *Arch. Int. Med.*, 66:319, Aug. 1940.
16. Farmer, Chester J.: The Detoxifying Action of Vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid) in Arsenical Therapy, *J. A. M. A.*, 1692, Nov. 15, 1941.
17. Greenbaum, Regina S.: The Detoxifying Action of Vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid) in Arsenical Therapy. *J. A. M. A.*, 1692, Nov. 15, 1941.
18. Harde, E.; Rothstein, I. A., and Ratish, H. D.: Urinary Excretion of Vitamin C in Pneumonia, *Proc. Soc. Exper. Biol. & Med.* 32:1088, 1935.
19. Holman, E.: Vitamin and Protein Factors in Preoperative and Postoperative Care of the Surgical Patient, *Surg., Gynec. & Obst.* 70:261, 1940.
20. Hunt, A. H.: The Role of Vitamin C in Wound Healing, *Brit. J. Surg.* 28:436, 1941.
21. Ingalls, T. H., and Warren, H. A.: Asymptomatic Scurvy, *New England J. Med.* 217:443, 1937.
22. Jackson, D. E.: The Peripheral Action of Certain Drugs with Special Reference to the Lungs. *J. Pharmacol. & Exper. Therap.* 4:291, 1913.
23. Jonnard, R. t Ruskin, S. L.: Etude Physico Chemique Comparee du Gluconate, du Cevitamate de calcium et de la Vitamine C. Submitted C. R. Soc. de Biologie, Paris, Reb., 1938.
24. Jonnard, R. and Ruskin, S. L.: Etude physico-comparee du gluconate, du sel de calcium de la vitamine C et la itamine C. *Compt. rend. Soc. de biol.*, 28:266, 1938.
25. King, C. G.: Vitamin C, Ascorbic Acid, *Physiol. Rev.* 16:238, 1936.
26. Lanman, T. H., and Ingalls, T. H.: Vitamin C Deficiency and Wound Healing, *Ann. Surg.* 105:616, 1937.
27. Lauber, H. J.: Vitamins and Healing of Wounds and Burns, *Bietr. z.klin. Chir.* 158:293, 1933.
28. Lund, C. C.: The Effect of Surgical Operations on the Level of Cevitamic Acid in the Blood Plasma, *New England J. Med.* 221:123, 1939.
29. Macht, D. I.; Ting, G. C.: Response to Drugs of Excised Bronchi from Normal and Diseased Animals, *J. Pharmacol. & Exper. Therap.* 18:111, 1921.
30. Macklin, C. C.: Musculature of Bronchi and Lungs. *Physiol. Rev.* 9:1, 1929.
31. Moon, Virgil H.: The Vascular and Cellular Dynamics of Shock. Monograph Blood Substitute and Blood Transfusion. Stuart Mudd and Wm. Thalhimer, Charles C. Thomas, Publisher, 1942.
32. Ruskin, S. L.: The Influence of Vitamin C on Wassermann Fastness in Syphilis, *Am. J. Digest. Dis.* 10:170, 1943.
33. Ruskin, S. L.: Studies on the Parallel Action of Vitamin C and Calcium, *Am. J. Digest. Dis.* 5:408, 1938.
34. Ruskin, S. L. and Silberstein, M.: The Influence of Vitamin C on the Therapeutic Activity of Bismuth, Antimony and the Arsenic Group of Metals. *Med. Rec.* 153:327, 1941.
35. Ruskin, S. L. and Jonnard, R.: Studies in Calcium Metabolism: Further Contributions to the Comparative Studies of the Physico-Chemical Properties of the Gluconate and Cevitamate of Calcium and of Vitamin C. Reprint. *Am. J. Dig. Disc.*, Vol. V—No. 10, pp. 676-680. Dec.
36. Sollman, T.: Gilbert, A. J.: Microscopic Observations of Bronchiolar Reactions, *J. Pharmacol. & Exper. Therap.* 61:272, 1937.
37. Sollman, T. A. Manual of Pharmacology. W. B. Saunders Co., 1943.
38. Sulzberger, M. G. and Oser, B.: Influence of Ascorbic Acid in Diet — On Sensitization of Guinea Pigs to Neoarsphenamine. *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.*, 34:716-719, 1934.
39. Taffel, M., and Harvey, S. C.: The Effect of Absolute and Partial Vitamin C Deficiency on Healing of Wounds, *Proc. Soc. Exper. Biol. & Med.* 38:518, 1938.
40. vonJeney, A., and Toro, I.: The Effect of Ascorbic Acid on the Formation of Fibers in Fibroblast Cultures, *Virchows Arch. f. path. Anat.* 298:87, 1936.
41. Wolbach, S. B., and Howe, P. R.: Intercellular Substances in Experimental Scorbutus, *Arch. Path.* 1: 1-24 (Jan.) 1926.
42. Went, A.; Martin, J.: Serum Sensitization. *Arch. Exper. Path. in Pharmacol.* 193:303, 1939.
43. Youmans, J. B.: Corlette, M. B.; Akeroyd, J. H., and Frank, H.: Studies of Vitamin C excretion and Saturation, *Am. J. M. Sc.* 191:319, 1936.
44. Cannon and Britton, *American J. of Physiol.* 1927.
45. Crane, M. M.; Woods, P. W.; Waters, E. M., and Murphy, E. F., *J. Nutrition*, 19, 16, 1940.
46. Minot, A. S.; Dodd, K.; Keller, M.; and Frank, H., *J. Pediat.* 16, 717, 1940.
47. Mouriquand, S., and Edel V., *Presse Med.* 51:353-4, 1943; *Chem. Zeit.* 1943, II, 1476.
48. Ruskin, S. L.: Influence of Vitamin C on the Anti-Histamine Action of Various Drugs, *Arch. of Otolaryng.* 36:853-873, 1942.

49. Ruskin, S. L.: Contribution to Study of Grippe Otitis, Myringitis Bullosa Hemorrhagica and Its Relationship to Latent Scurvy, *Laryngoscope* 48:327, 1938.
50. Ruskin, S. L.: Vitamin C-Sulfonamide Compounds In The Healing of Wounds, *Arch. of Otolaryngology*, 40:115-122, 1944.
51. Ruskin, S. L.: The Therapeutic Use of the Amino Acid Histidine in Allergy and Shock — "Histidine as a Factor in Histamine Epinephrine Balance", *J. Dig. Disc.*, II No. 7, July 1944.
52. Youmans, J. B.: Proceedings of the Eighteenth Annual Conference of the Milbank Memorial Fund, Milbank Memorial Fund, 1940.
53. Hamil, B. M.; Reynolds, C.; Poole, M. W., and Macy, I. G., *Am. J. Diseases of Child*, 56, 561, 1938.
54. Marchmont-Robinson, S. W., *J. Lab. & Clin. Med.* 26: 1478-81, 1941.
55. Laundau, S. W., and Gay, L. N.: Influence of Certain Amino Acids on Histamine Reactions and Anaphylactic Reactions in Intestinal Strips of Guinea Pigs and in Intact Guinea Pigs; *Bulletin of The Johns Hopkins Hospital* Vo. 74 No. 1:55-76, January 1944.

Globin Insulin: A Clinical Study

By

ABRAHAM TRASOFF, M.D., F.A.C.P.*

CHARLES BORDEN, M.D.**

SOLOMON S. MINTZ, M.D.***

PHILADELPHIA, PA.

EVERY clinician who treats diabetic patients is confronted with the problem of stabilization of that metabolic disorder either by diet alone or with the assistance of insulin. When insulin becomes necessary, it is for obvious reasons, to the advantage of the patient to have as few injections per day as possible. From this point of view regular insulin and crystalline insulin have been found wanting. When Hagedorn and his associates introduced protamine insulin, which was later modified by Scott and Fisher by the addition of zinc to be known as "Protamine Zinc Insulin", it was thought that the answer to "one daily dose" of insulin was finally found. However, as clinical experience with this form of insulin accumulated it became evident that there are a number of patients who require the addition of regular insulin for proper stabilization. It was also found that, due to the precipitating effect of the excess protamine in protamine zinc insulin, both forms of insulin could not be introduced in the same syringe, but had to be administered separately. Recently attempts to use mixtures of protamine zinc insulin and regular insulin have been reported, either by means of specially prepared mixtures, (1, 2, 3), or by any graded extemporaneous mixtures. These methods have not won wide acceptance, being viewed as too complicated.

Within the past five years a number of reports on globin insulin have appeared in the American Literature (6, 7, 8, 9, 10). They are almost unanimous in their praise of globin insulin as superior to protamine zinc insulin. Its merit according to these investigators consists in the following:—

1. Globin insulin will control practically all diabetics with one daily injection.

* Chief of Medical Service #2, Mount Sinai Hospital, Philadelphia.

** Jr. Adjunct, Metabolic Clinic, Mount Sinai Hospital, Philadelphia.

*** Chief Resident Physician, Mount Sinai Hospital, Philadelphia.

From the medical service of Dr. Abraham Trasoff, Mount Sinai Hospital, Philadelphia.

† The globin insulin used in this study was furnished by Burroughs Wellcome Co. U. S. A.

2. Globin insulin has a greater effect, unit for unit, than protamine zinc insulin. Hence, smaller doses of insulin are required.

3. Since the maximum effect of globin insulin is reached within 12 hours, hypoglycemic reactions, if they occur, will take place in the early evening, rather than during the night as with protamine; therefore they can be better controlled.

4. No allergic reactions occur with globin.

We became interested in globin insulin especially because of difficulties encountered with some diabetic patients treated in our Out-Patient Department with protamine zinc insulin. We therefore decided to hospitalize these patients and undertake a study of them, as well as of other severe diabetics admitted to Medical Ward, in order to compare the clinical effects of protamine zinc insulin and globin insulin. Particularly we wished to discover whether patients requiring separate injections of both protamine and standard insulin could be controlled with one dose of globin insulin.

PROCEDURE

Our plan was to give the patients a diet of caloric value suitable to their state of nutrition, with the carbohydrate content divided into 2/10 at breakfast, 2/10 at lunch and 6/10 at dinner. They were then stabilized with protamine zinc insulin alone or with a supplementary dose of regular insulin if necessary. Following this the diet was readjusted so as to give the maximum carbohydrate content during the noon meal, e.g. 2/10, 5/10, 3/10. Then globin insulin, usually 2/3 of the protamine zinc insulin requirement, was administered and stabilization attempted.

RESULTS

16 patients were studied, 5 of whom had previously been treated in our Diabetic Out-Patient Department. Table 1 shows the results in 10 patients of the group who were regulated satisfactorily with protamine zinc insulin alone. 6 of these required from 5-30 units less of globin insulin than of protamine zinc insulin to